

09-10

MAY

2024

4TH MEETING OF YOUNG BIOPHYSICISTS

BIOPHYSICS

FESTIVAL

UBI | COVILHÃ

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

ORGANIZATION

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Vicente Ledesma iMED.Ulisboa, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade de Lisboa (FFUL)

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Rita Guedes iMED.Ulisboa, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade de Lisboa (FFUL)

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Organization and partners

Welcome Message from the Portuguese Biophysics Society

Fellow Biophysicists,

Welcome to the Biophysics Festival 2024!

The Biophysics Festivals bring together young researchers passionate about biophysics to exchange knowledge, collaborate, celebrate scientific advancements, and informally socialize. This is already the 4th edition, and therefore it is fair to say that the Festivals are becoming a tradition in Portuguese Biophysics. They are organized by the Portuguese Young Biophysicists (PYBphy) group. And what a dedicated and resourceful Group it is! PYBphy has kept improving the Festivals, innovating at each new edition. So, the previous edition introduced a pre-Festival workshop, allowing participants to understand the basics of state-of-the-art Biophysics methods. The present edition, introduces bursaries to motivate the participation of young biophysicists from abroad. I hope that after attending the Festival these biophysicists will feel motivated to engage with or initiate similar groups and initiatives in their own countries, and that one day there will be an European Young Biophysicists Network!

The bursaries and other activities are funded thanks to the sponsorship from numerous institutions that this dynamic Organizing Committee managed to engage. Among those, the “Diamond Sponsors” IUPAB, EBSA, and BPI – Fundação “laCaixa”, are highlighted for their generous support.

A very positive outcome of PYBphy’s investment in the Festival is the increased attendance. 120 registered participants in this edition is a remarkable turnout for a scientific youth event in a country the size of Portugal. I am sure this attendance will enjoy the high-quality scientific presentations, productive scientific discussions, and great opportunities for informal socialization that are becoming the hallmarks of Biophysics Festivals.

We hope that these events will mobilize new scientists – even those biophysicists who did not use to regard themselves as such – to join the Portuguese Biophysical Society, thereby enjoying the many benefits of membership. Together, we can further energize Biophysics in Portugal.

Wishing you all a productive and merry Biophysics Festival. Enjoy the fascinating world of biophysics and be happy!

Armindo Salvador

President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society

Welcome Message from The Organizing Committee

Dear Esteemed Attendees,

We extend a warm welcome to you on behalf of the Portuguese Young Biophysicists (PYBphy) group within the Portuguese Biophysics Society!

It is with great excitement that we welcome you to the 4th Meeting of Young Biophysicists – the "Biophysics Festival 2024" – to be held at the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Beira Interior (UBI) in Covilhã.

Our primary aim is to facilitate connections among students and young scientists who share a passion for Biophysics. Our conference is designed to provide a relaxed and open atmosphere conducive to idea exchange and networking. It's not just about presenting research; it's about fostering meaningful interactions and friendships throughout these two days.

This event wouldn't be possible without the generous contributions of many. We extend our heartfelt thanks to the Faculty of Sciences of UBI for graciously hosting us and collaborating on a joint seminar. We're also grateful to our sponsors, esteemed speakers, and the dedicated Scientific Committee for their invaluable support. And to all our participants, your presence adds tremendous value to our gathering.

We are dedicated to ensuring that this meeting is both enriching and memorable for everyone involved. We eagerly anticipate your participation and look forward to seeing you there!

Warm regards,

The Young Portuguese Biophysicists Group

Program

9th of May

13h00-14h00 – Registration

14h00-14h15 – Opening Session

Dr. José Páscoa, Vice-Rector for Internationalization from UBI

Dr. Paulo Almeida, President of the Faculty of Sciences from UBI

Dr. Luís Taborda Barata, Health Sciences Research Centre, CICS-UBI, Coordinator

Dr. Armindo Salvador, President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society, SPBf

M.Sc. André Miranda, Representative of the Organizing Committee, PYBphy

Scientific Session 1

Chairs: Dr. Paula Gameiro and Dr. Armindo Salvador

Oral Presentations

14h15-14h35

OP1. HDX-MS AS A TOOL FOR SMALL MOLECULE BINDING CHARACTERIZATION: MONITORING MODULATION OF HUMAN CYCLOPHILIN D

Catarina F. Malta - iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica

OP2. MICRORNAS MULTIPLE DETECTION BY MOLECULAR BEACONS FOR ALZHEIMER DISEASE DIAGNOSTIC

Micaela Riscado - CICS-UBI – Health Sciences Research Centre, University of Beira Interior

14h35-14h40 - Q&A Session

Flash Presentations

14h40-15h05

FP1. A PALLADIUM COMPLEX AGAINST BREAST CANCER: METABOLIC IMPACT ANALYSIS BY RAMAN MICROSCOPY

Clara B. Martins - Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra

FP2. CERVICAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA DIAGNOSIS BY FTIR MICROSCOPY

Maria M. Félix - Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra

FP3. INSIGHTS INTO THE EFFECT OF GLUCOSE ON THE BINDING BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND THE NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUG NIMESULIDE

Otávio Augusto Chaves - CQC-IMS, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra

FP4. LYOTROPIC LIQUID CRYSTALLINE NANOASSEMBLIES: ADVANCED MULTIFUNCTIONAL NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER TREATMENT

Patrícia V. Teixeira - CF-UM-UP—Centro de Física das Universidades do Minho e Porto, Departamento de Física, Universidade do Minho

FP5. THE PUZZLING ARSENITE OXIDASE REACTION MECHANISM: PUTTING THE PIECES TOGETHER

Filipa Engrola - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

15h05-15h15 - Q&A Session

EBSA Plenary Lecture 1

15h15-16h15 - THE IMPORTANCE OF WATER IN MEMBRANE RECEPTOR FUNCTION

Professor Anthony Watts – University of Oxford

16h15-17h00 - Coffee-break & Poster Session

Scientific Session 2

Chairs: Dr. Cláudio Soares and Dr. Margarida Archer

Oral Presentations

17h00-17h40

OP3. NOVEL AFFINITY REAGENT FOR SARS-COV-2 VIRUS-LIKE PARTICLES

Carlos Costa - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

OP4. HOW CAN PROTONATION INFLUENCE CONFORMATIONAL SWITCHING: THE CURIOUS MECHANISM OF DIPHTHERIA TOXIN TRANSLOCATION (T-) DOMAIN

Nuno F. B. Oliveira - BioISI: Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa

OP5. $\alpha V\beta 3$ INTEGRIN PEPTIDE INHIBITORS IMPACT ON FIBRINOGEN ERYTHROCYTE BINDING

Catarina S. Lopes - Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa

OP6. UNCOVERING THE SECRETS OF GEOBACTER URANIREDUCENS: EXPLORING ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS FOR URANIUM BIOREMEDIATION

Alexandre Almeida - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

17h40-17h50 - Q&A Session

Flash Presentations

17h50-18h20

FP6. COMBINING COMPUTATIONAL AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS TO DEVELOP TAILOR-MADE BIOPHARMACEUTICALS TARGETING INFLUENZA A HEMAGGLUTININ

Madalena C. Marques - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

FP7. COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF NOVEL ANTIVIRALS THAT TARGET THE ZIKA VIRUS ENVELOPE PROTEIN DOMAIN III

Benedita Pereira - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

FP8. COMPUTATIONAL EVIDENCES OF A MISFOLDING EVENT IN AN AGGREGATION-PRONE LIGHT CHAIN PRECEDING THE FORMATION OF THE NON-NATIVE PATHOGENIC DIMER

Fausta Desantis - The Open University Affiliated Research Centre at Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia

FP9. EXPLORING EARLY-ON PROTONATION DYNAMICS ASSOCIATED WITH THE (DE)ACTIVATION OF CLASS A GPCRS

João N. M. Vitorino - BiolSI, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa

FP10. REVOLUTIONIZING ALZHEIMER'S TREATMENT: HARNESSING PHOTOSWITCHABLE MOLECULES THROUGH CUTTING-EDGE IN SILICO METHODS IN NEUROSCIENCE

Diana L. Assis - Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon

FP11. STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTION OF A HUMAN MOLECULAR MACHINE: THE RUVBL1/RUVBL2 COMPLEX AND THEIR ROLE IN PAQOSOME

Ana C. F. Paiva - iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica

18h20-18h30 - Q&A Session

18h30-18h45 - Group Photo

18h45-22h00 - Biophysics Party + Speed Networking

Núcleo do Sporting, Covilhã

10th of May

Scientific Session 3

Chairs: Dr. Sandra Ribeiro and Dr. Arménio Barbosa

SPBF Young Biophysicist Prize - Plenary Lecture 2

09h30-09h50 - ROTATION OF THE c-RING PROMOTES THE CURVATURE SORTING OF MONOMERIC ATP SYNTHASES

Dr. Marcin Makowski, SPBF Young Biophysicist Prize – Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Oral Presentations

09h50-10h10

OP7. EXPLORING pH-DEPENDENT DYNAMICS OF DOXORUBICIN DELIVERY USING FUNCTIONALIZED MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES: INSIGHTS FROM MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

Fábio G. Martins - LAQV/REQUIMTE, BioSIM Department of Biomedicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Porto

OP8. RATIONAL DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF ANTIVIRAL PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

Rita I. Teixeira - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier da Universidade de Lisboa

10h10-10h15 - Q&A Session

Flash Presentations

10h15-10h35

FP12. DESIGNING THE FUTURE OF CANCER IMMUNOTHERAPY: A COMPUTATIONAL STRATEGY FOR DUAL INHIBITION OF TIGIT AND PD-L1 PROTEINS

Rodrigo Barriga - Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon

FP13. DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF A MULTI-LEVEL COMPUTATIONAL AND IN VITRO APPROACH FOR IDENTIFYING MAPK3 INHIBITORS IN LEISHMANIA MARTINIQUENSIS AND LEISHMANIA ORIENTALIS

Duangnapa Kiriwan - LAQV/REQUIMTE, BioSIM - Departamento de Biomedicina, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade do Porto

FP14. FROM IN SILICO TO THE WET LAB: PAVING THE WAY IN LCP FAMILY INHIBITION

João Paquete-Ferreira - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

FP15. TARGETING THE CIRCADIAN CLOCK AND ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A STRUCTURE-BASED STRATEGY TO DISCOVER OREXIN RECEPTOR PHOTOSWITCHES

Vicente Ledesma-Martin - Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, Universidade de Lisboa

10h35-10h45 - Q&A Session

10h45-11h30 - Coffee-break & Poster Session

Scientific Session 4

Chair: Dr. Miguel Castanho

Plenary Lecture 3

11h30-12h30 – QUADRUPLICES ARE EVERYWHERE!

Dr. Jean-Louis Mergny, École Polytechnique

12h30-14h30 - Lunch break

Scientific Session 5

Chairs: Dr. Maria João Moreno and Dr. Nuno Santos

Oral Presentations

14h30-14h50

OP9. GRAPHENE/LIPID NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER IMAGING AND TREATMENT

Henrique Araújo-Silva - Centre of Molecular and Environmental Biology (CBMA)/Aquatic Research Network (ARNET) Associate Laboratory, University of Minho

OP10. PEGYLATED LIPID-BASED NANOCARRIERS FOR THE TREATMENT OF RETINOPATHIES: DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION

Maria João Faria - Centre of Physics of Minho and Porto Universities (CF-UM-UP), Universidade do Minho

14h50-14h55 - Q&A Session

Flash Presentations

14h55-15h20

FP16. BIOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF AGING NUCLEAR MEMBRANES: IMPLICATIONS FROM MODEL SYSTEMS

Aivaras Vilutis - Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa

FP17. MOLECULAR RECOGNITION OF MULTIVALENT GLYCOMIMETICS BY HUMAN MACROPHAGE GALACTOSE-TYPE LECTIN

Aleandra Travecedo - UCIBIO, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology

FP18. UNVEILING DRUG-LIPID INTERACTIONS: A SYNCHROTRON-BASED FTIR STUDY

João Santos - Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra

FP19. TOXICITY ASSESSMENT OF THE PHOTOCATALYTIC PROCESS USING FERRITE NANOMATERIALS $Zn_{0.5}X_{0.5}Fe_2O_4$ (X=Mg, Cu): INSIGHTS FROM VIBRIO FISCHERI ON POLLUTANT REMOVAL EFFICIENCY

Ricardo J. C. Fernandes - Physics Centre of Minho and Porto Universities (CF-UM-UP), University of Minho

FP20. SHINING INSIGHT: PROBING LUNG CANCER CELLS WITH A NON-CONVENTIONAL PLATINUM COMPLEX

Jéssica D. Silva - Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra

15h20-15h30 - Q&A Session

15h30-15h45 - “La Caixa” Foundation

15h45-16h00 - Small Break

Scientific Session 5

Chairs: Dr. Manuel Prieto

IUPAB Plenary Lecture 4

16h00-17h00 - CALCIUM-PERMEABLE AMPA RECEPTORS: DYNAMICS AND REGULATION BY AUXILIARY SUBUNITS

Speaker: *Dr. Beatriz Herguedas - University of Zaragoza*

17h00-17h15 - Closing Session & Awards

Plenary Lectures

Overview

PL1. THE IMPORTANCE OF WATER IN MEMBRANE RECEPTOR FUNCTION

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PL2. ROTATION OF THE c-RING PROMOTES THE CURVATURE SORTING OF MONOMERIC ATP SYNTHASES

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PL3. QUADRUPLICES ARE EVERYWHERE!

Jean-Louis Mergny – École Polytechnique

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Beatriz Herguedas – Universidade de Zaragoza

Oral Presentations

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Ana C.F. Paiva, Philipp Busse, Paulo E. Santo, Sarah Cianférani, Xavier Manival, Célia Plisson-Chastang, Daniel Schwarz, Pedro M. Matias, Pedro M.F. Sousa, Tiago M. Bandeiras

FP12. DESIGNING THE FUTURE OF CANCER IMMUNOTHERAPY: A COMPUTATIONAL STRATEGY FOR DUAL INHIBITION OF TIGIT AND PD-L1 PROTEINS

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FP14. FROM IN SILICO TO THE WET LAB: PAVING THE WAY IN LCP FAMILY INHIBITION

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Jéssica D. Silva, Joana Marques, Inês P. Santos, Ana L.M. Batista de Carvalho, Clara B. Martins, Raquel C. Laginha, Luís A.E. Batista de Carvalho, M. Paula M. Marques

Poster Sessions

Overview

P1. DUPLEX-QUADRUPLEX COMPETITION AT PROMOTERS

Anne Cucchiari, Cyril Esnault, Jean-Christophe Andrau, Jean-Louis Mergny

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Plenary Lectures

Abstracts

EBSA Plenary Lecture 1

PL1. THE IMPORTANCE OF WATER IN MEMBRANE RECEPTOR FUNCTION

Anthony Watts
University of Oxford, Oxford, UK

Anthony (Tony) Watts, is an Emeritus Professor of Biochemistry and Leverhulme Fellow at the University of Oxford, UK, where he was on the faculty from 1980-2021 and trained over 70 graduate students. He is a fellow of the Royal Chemical Society, the Institute of Physics, Royal Society of Biology and Biophysical Society, as well as an Honorary Member of the British Biophysical Society and Hungarian Biophysical Society.

Tony was managing editor of *Biophysical Chemistry* (1991-2000), the *European Biophysics Journal* (2000-2015) and Associate Editor of the *Biophysical Journal* (2002-2009). Also, he was chair of the British Biophysical Society (2001-2007; 2009-2017), Executive Committee member (2000-2017) then President of EBSA (2017-2019), and elected President-elect of IUPAB in 2021.

During his PhD (Leeds University, Biophysics, 1975), Tony has focused on understanding how biological membranes function using a range of biophysical methods that include magnetic resonance (EPR, Solid State NMR), single molecule microscopy, X-ray and neutron diffraction, MSP, Mass Spec., MD simulation, always supported by functional assays. A major focus has been receptors, some of which are major drug targets (GPCRs), and photoreceptors (one of the most abundant classes of protein on the face of the earth). Recently, Tony has contributed to the study of the functional significance of receptor oligomerization using single

molecule and spectroscopic methods, and the fast changes induced by light in photoreceptors using time resolved, photoinduced XFELs. His research has gained him several awards and honours.

Despite being retired, Tony is still actively publishing, giving seminars, and is fully engaged with biophysics at the national and international level (EBSA, IUPAB, BBS), and co-editing the Encyclopaedia of Biophysics (Nature-Springer)

ABSTRACT

Resolving conformational changes in membrane receptors in response to a stimulus, and capturing their functionally relevant dynamics, is very challenging. Over the years we have addressed this challenge using a range of spectroscopic approaches^{1,2,3} on functionally competent photoreceptors, often in their natural membranes⁴ or LipodisqsTM ^{5,6}. More recently, we have complemented this work with functional studies, mass spec characterization⁷ and very high resolution (1.07Å) crystallography ^{8,9,10}, as well as photo-induced x-ray, free electron laser studies (XFELs), without the use of detergents and including natural lipids. This high-resolution information reveals waters and their importance in both receptor activation-desensitization and QM(SCC-DFTB)/MM MD trajectories give information about the activation process. The system studied is a rhodopsin-3 (AR3), a photoreceptor utilized widely in optogenetics despite the lack of structures until now. We suggest that the different arrangement of internal water networks in AR3 is responsible for the faster photocycle kinetics compared to homologs – AR3 is ~10x more efficient than bacteriorhodopsin at current generation. These insights may well have generic implications for other receptors.

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SPBF Young Biophysicist Prize - Plenary Lecture 2

PL2. ROTATION OF THE c-RING PROMOTES THE CURVATURE SORTING OF MONOMERIC ATP SYNTHASES

Marcin Makowski

Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Marcin Makowski, PhD in Biomedical Research specialty Biophysics (2023, IMM-ULisboa), is a Junior Researcher at the Universidad Complutense de Madrid since 2023.

M Makowski research is focused on biological membranes and their implications in health and disease and his main interests consist in studying 1) the membrane aggregation and activity, 2) the selectivity of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) on anionic membranes and more recently 3) the interactions between bimolecular motors and membranes.

M Makowski is a member of Real Sociedad Española de Química and Portuguese Biochemical Society (SPB). In 2028, M Makowski was awarded with Best Poster in Peptide Science at the Iberian Biophysics Congress, Castellón, Spain. In 2024, M Makowski was awarded the Prize for Young Biophysicist 2024, granted by the Portuguese Biophysical Society.

ABSTRACT

ATP synthases are proteins that catalyse the formation of ATP through the rotatory movement of their membrane-spanning subunit. In mitochondria, ATP synthases are found to arrange as dimers at the high-curved edges of *crístae*. Here, a direct link is explored between the rotatory movement of ATP synthases and their preference for curved membranes. An active curvature sorting of ATP synthases in lipid nanotubes pulled from giant vesicles is found. Coarse-grained simulations confirm the curvature-seeking behaviour of rotating ATP synthases, promoting reversible and frequent protein-protein contacts. The formation of transient protein dimers relies on the membrane-mediated attractive interaction of the order of $1.5k_B T$ produced by a hydrophobic mismatch upon protein rotation. Transient dimers are sustained by a conic-like arrangement characterized by a wedge angle of $\theta \approx 50^\circ$, producing a dynamic coupling between protein shape and membrane curvature. The results suggest a new role of the rotational movement of ATP synthases for their dynamic self-assembly in biological membranes.

Plenary Lecture 3

PL3. QUADRUPLEXES ARE EVERYWHERE!

Jean-Louis Mergny

*Ecole Polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Palaiseau,
France*

Jean-Louis Mergny leads a group working on unusual Nucleic Acid Structures in Ecole Polytechnique, Palaiseau, France. He is also Head of the Biology Department of Institut Polytechnique de Paris, and co-director of the Engineering for Health (E4H) interdisciplinary center.

JL Mergny's actual research activity is focused on the study of G-quadruplexes of nucleic acids, their interactions with drugs, and their applications to medicine and nanotechnology using chemical, biophysical, and biochemical methods. JL Mergny has published more than 300 articles in international journals (h-index= 91) and holds 20 international patents.

Mergny has been and elected member of Academia Europaea since 2029 and is the former head of the European Institute of Chemistry and Biology (IECB) in Pessac, near Bordeaux, France.

ABSTRACT

We are developing tools to study G-quadruplex formation and understand the folding and polymorphism of unusual nucleic acid structures, both *in vitro* and in cells¹. This allowed us to discover new DNA folds² and demonstrate that DNA i-motif levels are overwhelmingly depleted in living human cells³. In parallel, we are applying the G4Hunter algorithm⁴ (for the prediction of G4 propensity) to a variety of genomes, including archaea⁵, cancer⁶, parasite⁷ viral genomes⁸, as well as extinct genomes. We analysed the genomes of hepatitis B viruses (HBV) for the presence of G-quadruplex-forming sequences⁹. Our work used genomes from ancient and modern HBV stains and represents the first paleogenomic analysis of the propensity for G4 formation in any genome. We then performed a detailed analysis of G-quadruplex sequences in Neandertal mitochondrial DNA¹⁰. Relatively similar patterns were found compared to modern humans, in mitochondrial DNA with one notable exception, corresponding to a motif found in the D-loop region of mtDNA, which is responsible for mitochondrial DNA replication. This area is directly responsible for the number of mitochondria and consequently for the efficient energy metabolism of cell. Neandertals harbor a long uninterrupted run of guanines in this region, which may cause problems for replication, in contrast with anatomically modern humans, for which this run is generally shorter and interrupted.

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IUPAB Plenary Lecture 4

PL4. CALCIUM-PERMEABLE AMPA RECEPTORS: DYNAMICS AND REGULATION BY AUXILIARY SUBUNITS

Beatriz Herguedas

University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain

Beatriz Herguedas, PhD in Biochemistry (2011, University of Zaragoza, Spain), is a group leader of the Structural Biology and Biophysics group at Unizar Institute of Biocomputing and Physics of Complex Systems (BIFI), at the University of Zaragoza, Spain.

B. Herguedas research interests are focused on understanding membrane proteins at the atomic level, combining protein biochemistry, biophysics, and structural biology techniques. In 2019, B. Herguedas was awarded a “Ramón y Cajal” fellowship from the Spanish Research Agency, allowing her to start an independent career at the BIFI Institute, where she is now focused on the structure and dynamics of calcium permeable AMPARS and their complexes with auxiliary proteins.

B. Herguedas was the first to determine the structures of heteromeric AMPAR receptors and their interaction with auxiliary proteins using X-ray crystallography and cryo-EM techniques. B. Herguedas publishes actively and has presented her research in various international conferences and scientific seminars. She is also a lecturer in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology at the University of Zaragoza

Abstract

Introduction: AMPA-type glutamate receptors (AMPA) are tetrameric ion channels composed of different combinations of four subunits (GluA1 to GluA4) that mediate fast excitatory neurotransmission and synaptic plasticity. The GluA core interacts with a plethora of auxiliary proteins such as TARPs and CKAMPs, generating receptors with different functional properties, including calcium permeability, trafficking, kinetics and pharmacology. Determining the structure of different AMPARs is essential to understand the diverse functional properties of glutamate receptors and to identify novel routes of modulation.

Methodology: We used electron cryo-microscopy in combination with biochemistry and electrophysiology to analyze the structure of GluA4-containing AMPA receptor complexes, a model of calcium-permeable AMPARs.

Results: We determined the cryo-EM structures of GluA4 and GluA4-TARP complexes in different functional states, including resting, open, desensitized and apo-states. GluA4 receptors in resting and open state adopt an overall Y-shape conformation similar to other GluA receptors, with two Ligand Binding Domain (LBD) dimers which completely disrupt upon desensitization. Binding of 4 TARP subunits to the GluA4 core reduces dynamics but it does not prevent LBD dimer disruption. TARP extracellular loops interact with AMPARs at two different sites, slowing GluA4 desensitization and deactivation.

Conclusion: The structural proteome of AMPARs is expanded by the determination of the first structures of GluA4 containing receptors. Structures reveal their unique conformation during desensitization and the structural bases of their modulation by TARP auxiliary proteins.

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Abstracts

OP1. HDX-MS AS A TOOL FOR SMALL MOLECULE BINDING CHARACTERIZATION: MONITORING MODULATION OF HUMAN CYCLOPHILIN D

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Keywords: Hydrogen deuterium exchange mass spectrometry (HDX-MS), Fragment-based Drug Discovery (FBDD), Cyclophilin D (CypD), protein structure, protein dynamics, protein-ligand interactions, low affinity fragments, binding site detection, drug discovery.

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen deuterium exchange mass spectrometry (HDX-MS) is emerging as a powerful biophysical technique for probing protein interactions, structure, and conformational dynamics. While HDX-MS is well-established for the characterization of potent compounds binding to their target proteins there are only few examples in the literature regarding the application of HDX-MS to the study of low-affinity fragments and none describing the usage of HDX-MS for molecules with affinities in the mM range.

In our work, we use human Cyclophilin D (CypD) as a system to explore the possibility of using HDX-MS to characterize the binding of fragments with mM binding affinities. CypD is the mitochondrial isoform of Cyclophilins which plays an important role in the execution of cell death by regulating the mitochondrial permeability transition pore. Mitochondrial dysfunction has been implicated in a cascade of cellular processes related to several diseases such as multiple sclerosis and cardiovascular disease, making CypD an interesting target for therapeutic intervention.

HDX-MS was used to monitor the binding of fragments targeting three different pockets of CypD. Despite the weak binding affinities of these molecules (mM range) we could observe reduction in deuteration levels in CypD regions that match the different binding sites of the fragments. In a second step, we tested fragments with an unknown binding site. Careful analysis of the HDX-MS profiles obtained enabled the mapping of the different binding sites. Altogether our results show that HDX-MS could be a valuable tool in fragment-based drug design projects for the design and improvement of low-affinity CypD inhibitors.

OP2. MICRORNAS MULTIPLE DETECTION BY MOLECULAR BEACONS FOR ALZHEIMER DISEASE DIAGNOSTIC

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Keywords: *MicroRNAs, Molecular Beacons, Alzheimer's disease, Biomarkers*

ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease is a chronic neurodegenerative disorder characterized by A β -peptide depositions, and Tau protein hyperphosphorylation, leading to neurodegeneration. Studies have shown that it is associated with altered miRNA levels, including miRNA-29b and miRNA-9. So, these small non-coding RNAs involved in post-transcriptional gene expression regulation are promising biomarkers. Established miRNA detection methods are expensive and time-consuming, creating a need to develop a simple and low-cost diagnostic tool. Molecular beacons (MB) are nucleic acid probes with hairpin shape labeled with a reporter fluorophore at the 5' end and a quencher at the 3' end. This allows the rapid and cost-effective detection of complementary miRNAs with high specificity and sensitivity by Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET).

MB-29-1 and MB-9-1 were designed with loops complementary to the miRNA-29b-1-3p and the miRNA-9-1-5p, respectively. A double MB assay that can simultaneously quantify these miRNAs in complex samples, without interference from the precursor form, was optimized using FRET, Nucleic Magnetic Resonance, and circular dichroism spectroscopies to characterize the nucleic acids behavior and the MBs binding capacity to the target miRNAs.

MB hybridization to target miRNAs was optimized. Both MBs simultaneously detected and quantified the respective miRNA in complex and heterogeneous RNA samples, in a range between 0.013-0.8 μ M. No significant signal was detected in the presence of the precursor or unspecific miRNAs, showing the capacity to distinguish between the mature and precursor forms and other miRNAs.

The results confirm the MBs potential to become a powerful tool for assessing miRNAs as biomarkers.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), through the projects UIDB/00709/2020 and UIDP/00709/2020. Micaela Riscado acknowledges FCT for the Ph.D. fellowship 2021.07658.BD.

OP3. NOVEL AFFINITY REAGENT FOR SARS-COV-2 VIRUS-LIKE PARTICLES

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Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, spike protein, virus-like particles, affinity ligands.

ABSTRACT

Virus-like particles (VLPs) have been proven efficient vaccine candidates, with high immunogenicity due to their repetitive epitopes [1]. The need for SARS-CoV-2 VLPs persists, not only for vaccine development, but also to study virus assembly and entry mechanisms, in preparation for future pandemics [2]. However, purification of VLPs remains challenging [1]. We developed an affinity ligand based on the Petasis-Ugi scaffold for the purification of SARS-CoV-2 VLPs, targeting its spike protein. These ligands are easy, quick and inexpensive to synthesise, offering tuneable affinity for any desired target [3].

The design of affinity ligands involved the use of computational tools for their rational design based on structures of known natural binders and to simulate their interactions [4]. A 120-ligand combinatorial library was synthesised and screened experimentally against the spike protein in scaled-down chromatographic conditions. In parallel, docking of the combinatorial library against the spike protein receptor-binding domain was performed (AutoDock, Vina and MOE). The best-performing ligand yielded >95% binding and 65-75% recovery for wild type and BA.5 variant. Against clarified supernatant, the enrichment of spike protein after one run was of 29.3%. Molecular dynamics studies are ongoing to analyse the interactions involved between our top ligand and the spike protein.

We have successfully demonstrated a proof-of-concept methodology for the quick development of high-affinity, inexpensive, sustainable ligands towards the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 899732 (PURE Project); FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P.; within the scope of the project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 of UCIBIO; the project LA/P/0140/2020 of i4HB; with support by INGD, 2022.15912.CPCA.A1 and 2023.10436.CPCA.A1, funded by FCT and FEDER under the project 01/SAICT/2016 no. 02215; and PhD scholarship of C. C., 2020.07566.BD.

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OP4. HOW CAN PROTONATION INFLUENCE CONFORMATIONAL SWITCHING: THE CURIOUS MECHANISM OF DIPHTHERIA TOXIN TRANSLOCATION (T-) DOMAIN

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Keywords: *Constant pH simulations, pH effects, conformational switching, diphtheria toxin.*

ABSTRACT

Toxins and viruses have evolved as optimal membrane penetrating entities, often applying pH-triggering conformational transitions in this process [1,2]. An example of this feature is found in the translocation domain (T-domain) of the diphtheria toxin, which upon the late endosome medium acidification, protonates key amino acids to penetrate the membrane bilayer. Although the overall process is known and several residues have been found important to the process [3], the molecular details of such translocation are still not fully understood.

In our work, constant-pH MD simulations were applied to describe the effect of the pH in the starting steps of this translocation process. Employing mutations on key residues of the wt T-domain, we were able to combine our CpHMD data and NME data from our collaborators to identify the pH-dependent features of the first steps of the conformational transition. We verified the pH-triggering capabilities of H257 in this process and the impact of a strong latch-type mechanism between H223 and E259 which modulated the conformational transition trigger through electrostatic effects. Being capable of describing and understanding this complex process provides a crucial tool to help develop delivery systems based on this biological machinery, possibly targeting aggressive cancer cells whose tumor microenvironment is more acidic.

Acknowledgments: We acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia for funding through projects UIDB/04046/2020 & UIDP/04046/2020 and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and 2021.06409.BD.

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OP5. $\alpha_V\beta_3$ INTEGRIN PEPTIDE INHIBITORS IMPACT ON FIBRINOGEN ERYTHROCYTE BINDING

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Keywords: *erythrocyte, fibrinogen-erythrocyte interaction, $\alpha_V\beta_3$ integrin inhibitors, atomic force microscopy.*

ABSTRACT

Integrins play a crucial role in linking the cytoskeleton to the extracellular matrix^{1,2}. Previous studies identified the presence of the $\alpha_V\beta_3$ integrin on the erythrocyte membrane, acting as receptor for fibrinogen and contributing to increased cell-cell adhesion^{3,4}. This integrin specifically recognizes the Arg-Gly-Asp (RGD) domain present in extracellular matrix proteins and fibrinogen.

To investigate the impact of $\alpha_V\beta_3$ integrin inhibitors on fibrinogen-erythrocyte binding, four integrin inhibitor peptides were tested: cilengitide, 29¹, FRX025, and an $\alpha_V\beta_1$ ligand used as control. The interaction and its inhibition were assessed using atomic force microscopy (AFM)-based force spectroscopy and zeta potential measurements.

A significant reduction of fibrinogen-erythrocyte binding frequency was observed in the presence of these inhibitors. Notably, peptide 29 exhibited enhanced selectivity and efficacy compared to cilengitide. In the presence of 29 and fibrinogen, the erythrocyte surface charge is more negative than without this inhibitor.

These results indicate the efficacy of peptide 29 on inhibiting fibrinogen-erythrocyte binding, which may mitigate erythrocyte aggregation and improve microcirculation flow conditions. The targeting of the $\alpha_V\beta_3$ integrin may be used to develop potential therapies to reduce hypercoagulation in cardiovascular patients.

Acknowledgements: The work developed was funded by FCT-MCTES (Portugal) project PTDC/EMD-TLM/7289/2020, and the fellowships PD/BD/135045/2017 and COVID/BD/151823/2021.

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OP6. UNCOVERING THE SECRETS OF *GEOBACTER URANIIREDUCTENS*: EXPLORING ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS FOR URANIUM BIOREMEDIATION

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Keywords: *Geobacter*, *Bioremediation*, *Extracellular Electron Transfer*, *Multiheme Cytochromes*

ABSTRACT

Within the complex mechanisms of microbial systems, *Geobacter* species have emerged as crucial bacteria in the dynamics of environmental microbiology. These microorganisms present an impressive respiratory versatility being capable of couple the oxidation of a wide range of organic compounds to the reduction of either soluble or insoluble electron acceptors in their respiratory processes, by a mechanism known as extracellular electron transfer (EET) [1]. A distinctive hallmark of *Geobacter* bacteria is a conserved family formed by 4 to 6 triheme cytochromes. These families have been studied in *G. sulfurreducens* (*Gs*) and *G. metallireducens* (*Gm*) and the functional properties have revealed notable differences in their EET mechanisms, paving the way for other species to be target of investigation. One environmentally relevant *Geobacter* strain, *Geobacter uraniireducens*, is part of these efforts. *Geobacter uraniireducens* shares numerous metabolic similarities with *Gs* and was originally isolated from subsurface sediments contaminated with uranium [2]. In this work, we performed a detailed functional and thermodynamic characterization of two members of the family of triheme cytochromes from *G. uraniireducens* by the complementary usage of NMR and visible spectroscopic techniques. The data show that the *G. uraniireducens*' triheme cytochromes have unique properties compared to their homologs in *Gs* and *Gm*, including less-negative heme reduction potentials, which are modulated by the redox interactions and just in one case additionally by redox-Bohr interactions, aside from an unprecedented oxidation order of the hemes. These results start to reveal the secrets of the uranium reduction pathways, shedding light how strategies to bioremediate toxic contaminants in the environment can be explored.

Acknowledgements:

Supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia through the grant PTDC/BIABQM/4967/2020 and by FCT projects UIDP/04378/2020, UIDB/04378/2020, LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB).

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OP7. EXPLORING pH-DEPENDENT DYNAMICS OF DOXORUBICIN DELIVERY USING FUNCTIONALIZED MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES: INSIGHTS FROM MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *MD Simulations, Carbon Nanotubes, Cancer*

ABSTRACT

Doxorubicin, a widely used chemotherapeutic agent, faces challenges due to dose-dependent side effects, necessitating innovative delivery strategies. Nanocarriers, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), have the potential ability to mitigate these challenges by performing targeted drug delivery and therefore reducing adverse effects. However, CNTs tend to aggregate in tissues, therefore, functionalization of these structures is essential to address solubility issues and enhance efficacy.

Initially, a pristine, dual-layer carbon nanotube model was created, followed by preparation of five additional models through functionalization with carboxylic acid, lysine, lactose bound to lysine, mannose bound to lysine, and galactose bound to lysine. Subsequently doxorubicin molecules were added using packmol. Two variations of each system were created, one for neutral and other for acidic pH. Molecular dynamics simulations were conducted using the Amber20 software package. These simulations had 300 ns in length.

MD simulations revealed pH-dependent adsorption patterns, with neutral pH conditions having higher adsorption levels of Doxorubicin when compared to acidic pH. Furthermore, carbohydrate-modified lysinated MWCNTs exhibited enhanced adsorption compared to pristine or carboxylated nanotubes, indicating an increased advantage for these functionalized groups.

This study highlights the potential of functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes for efficient doxorubicin delivery to cancer cells, offering valuable insights into drug-nanotube interactions and paving the way for further optimization in drug delivery systems.

Acknowledgements: This work received financial support from FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020, and 2021.07128.BD) through national funds. This work received support and help from FCT/MCTES (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020 and UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020), through national funds.

OP8. RATIONAL DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF ANTIVIRAL PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

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Keywords: *ARMY, anti-SARS-CoV-2 therapeutic, Molecular Dynamics, Protein Design, RBD*

ABSTRACT

Targeting viral entry has been a promising therapeutic approach in the quest to contain the spread of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Here, triple helical bundle antiviral proteins (ARMYs) were computationally designed and optimized to target the Spike protein receptor-binding domain (RBD) and block it from binding angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2).

The design strategy considers the molecular details of the RBD-ACE2 binding, by incorporating into the backbone scaffolds the two ACE2 adjacent α -helices which account for most of the interactions with the RBD. Aiming to stabilize the two interacting helices, a short loop and a third helix were inserted into the scaffold. Moreover, the amino acid sequences were designed to optimize target binding, folding and stability. Further validation was performed using structural prediction methods. Five candidate proteins were experimentally tested. Lastly, molecular dynamics simulations of the designs were performed in the unbound and the bound state to RBD, to assess their stability and key intermolecular interactions that may affect the binding affinity.

Experimental assays demonstrated that four of the five designed proteins (ARMYs 1-4) effectively bind the RBD with nanomolar affinity, which is comparable with the ACE2 affinity for Spike, and successfully blocked SARS-CoV-2 infection in cell assays. Simulations of these designs elucidated the conformational dynamics that may affect the binding. ARMY 5 demonstrated a distinct dynamic behavior from the others.

The design strategy implemented resulted in starting points for novel anti-SARS-CoV-2 therapeutics. Continued method improvement enables to develop high-affinity designs for a rapid response to future pandemics.

Acknowledgments:

This work was supported by LaCaixa Foundation, within the projects "The BioPlATTAR Platform for the Tailored and Rapid Development of Antiviral Biopharmaceuticals" and "EvaMobs, a Horizon Europe Framework Programme, under reference HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03-04, ID 101137419", and by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (PhD Scholarship: 023.00583.BD, iNOVA4Health: UIDB/04462/2020, MostMicro: UIDP/04612/2020, LS4Future: LA/P/0087/2020).

OP9. GRAPHENE/LIPID NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER IMAGING AND TREATMENT

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Keywords: *Graphene, Doxorubicin, Nanocarrier, Cancer, Theranostics.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer remains a prominent cause of death, with estimates pointing to a 77% increase in the number of new cancer cases between 2022 and 2050. Present chemotherapeutic agents can induce toxicity, even at therapeutic doses, and become ineffective by multidrug resistance (MDR) development. Doxorubicin (DOX), a powerful chemotherapeutic, kills fast-growing cancer cells, but also displays toxicity in healthy tissues. Commercial DOX formulations have the disadvantage of increasing DOX aggregation and MDR. Aggregates are less effective in DNA intercalation, decreasing DOX therapeutic efficacy.

In-house made nanographene oxide (NGO) or commercial graphene oxide quantum dots (GQD) were conjugated with DOX (GQD/NGO@DOX) and inserted in nonlamellar lipid carriers to improve biodistribution. GQD possess photoluminescence providing a bio tracking tool for DOX release. DOX release is pH-triggered at the acidic pH of cancer cells. Therefore, this work aspires to enhance DOX therapeutic effect, selectivity, and pH-triggered drug release profile, allowing to trace drug delivery through imaging.

NGO were synthesized and together with commercial GQD were thoroughly characterized. GQD/NGO@DOX cytotoxicity was evaluated in L929 reference cell line and in zebrafish embryos (*Danio rerio*) through fish acute embryotoxicity (FET) assay according with the OECD test guideline (TG) 236, drawing the toxicological profile of these new conjugates. This strategy allowed the identification of the conjugates that show better performance in relation to free DOX and simultaneously allow for theranostic applications.

Current cancer treatment strategies present major drawbacks, some of which can be circumvented by our new pH-triggered nano-delivery systems, raising opportunity to tackle the ever-increasing cancer numbers.

OP10. PEGYLATED LIPID-BASED NANOCARRIERS FOR THE TREATMENT OF RETINOPATHIES: DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION

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Keywords: *Lipid nanocarriers, Topical ophthalmic delivery, Retina, Posterior segment of the eye, Contact Lenses.*

ABSTRACT

Age-related retinal diseases (ARRD) are among the leading causes of blindness worldwide, and their prevalence is expected to rise as the population ages. Hence, it is critical to develop new non-invasive treatment options to avoid the frequent intraocular injections to the posterior segment of the eye.

In this study, a topical ophthalmic drug delivery system was developed to promote interaction with the ocular surface and enhance penetration to intraocular tissues. Specifically, PEGylated lipid-based nanocarriers (LN) enriched with monoolein (MO@LN) and phytantriol (PHY@LN) were evaluated regarding their physicochemical properties (size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, stability, and thermodynamic behavior) using dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering. Optimized MO@LN and PHY@LN were also characterized *in vitro* for their encapsulation efficiency of resveratrol, for their ocular irritation potential using the Hen's egg test on the chorioallantoic membrane (HET-CAM), and for their hemocompatibility. Finally, MO@LN and PHY@LN were incorporated (soaking method) in contact lenses (CL) made of four different materials, and their impact on CL transmittance, thickness, and power was tested.

Both MO@LN and PHY@LN showed suitable physicochemical properties (< 300 nm; > +50 mV; PDI < 0.3; stable for 4 weeks) for a balanced interaction with the corneal surface and penetration along the eye. Moreover, the encapsulation of RSV was high (> 85 %) for both LN, and they neither caused irritation in chicken embryos nor promoted hemolysis of erythrocytes. CL intrinsic properties were not significantly altered with LN incorporation. Overall, MO@LN and PHY@LN seem promising drug delivery systems for the treatment of retinopathies.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) in the framework of the Strategic Funding UIDB/04650/2020. M. J. Faria acknowledges FCT I.P. for PhD grant (2020.06561.BD).

FLASH PRESENTATIONS

Abstracts

FP1. A PALLADIUM COMPLEX AGAINST BREAST CANCER: METABOLIC IMPACT ANALYSIS BY RAMAN MICROSCOPY

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Keywords: *palladium, triple-negative breast cancer, Raman microscopy, cisplatin resistance.*

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer remains the leading cause of death among women worldwide, with 685,000 deaths in 2020. Triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) is the most aggressive subtype, associated with rapid disease progression, a worse prognosis, higher and earlier rates of recurrence and death. Improved chemotherapeutic approaches against TNBC are therefore an urgent clinical need, targeting malignant cells with minimal damage to the healthy ones. Raman vibrational spectroscopy is a promising tool in medicinal chemistry, since it is a non-invasive, reproducible, cost-effective and highly accurate analytical technique [2,3]. The aim of this study is to assess the metabolic impact of a trinuclear Pd(II) complex with spermidine (Pd_3Spd_2) on: i) cisplatin-sensitive TNBC (MDA-MB-231) and ii) cisplatin-resistant TNBC (MDA-MB-231/R); iii) non-cancerous human breast cells (MCF-12A). The cells were seeded on MgF_2 disks, treated with Pd_3Spd_2 IC_{50} concentrations for 48h, and formalin fixed. Raman spectra were acquired for both untreated and drug-treated cells. The MATLAB and Quasar 1.5 software packages were used for spectral pre-processing and data analysis. Chemical differences among cell lines probed were clearly unveiled, upon principal component analysis (PCA) of the spectroscopic data. These results provided spectral characteristics specific to malignancy and allowed to identify particular biochemical reporters (spectral biomarkers) that led to the discrimination between drug-treated cells and untreated ones.

This improved knowledge of the drug cellular targets constitutes a paramount advance in cancer treatment, particularly regarding a type of malignancy with a high morbidity and mortality. In addition, this knowledge is expected to foster the development of improved anticancer drugs.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology within the scope of the Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit Strategic Program UIDB/00070/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/00070/2020>) & UIDP/00070/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/00070/2020>), the C. B. Martins PhD Grant (SFRH/BD/08869/2021) and the A.L.M.B.d.C. employment contract (<https://doi.org/10.54499/CECIND/00069/2017/CP1460/CT0029>).

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FP2. CERVICAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA DIAGNOSIS BY FTIR MICROSCOPY

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Keywords: *Cervical cancer, FTIR microspectroscopy, cryopreserved cervical tissue, SVM.*

ABSTRACT

In 2020, cervical cancer ranked as the fourth most prevalent cancer globally [1]. Detecting the tumor early is crucial for reducing mortality rates. Unfortunately, this type of cancer disproportionately affects developing countries, primarily due to limited access to Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination and screening programs [2,3,4,5]. Consequently, there's an urgent need for innovative approaches to reliably screen and diagnose precancerous and cancerous cervical lesions.

Vibrational spectroscopy, notably microFTIR, was employed to analyze cryopreserved human cervical tissue samples, including SCC and non-cancerous ones from the Portuguese Oncology Institute-Porto. A Support Vector Machine classification model distinguished between normal and malignant samples, achieving over 90% accuracy through cross-validation.

MicroFTIR successfully discerned between normal and malignant cervical tissue samples with high accuracy, leveraging a specialized Support Vector Machine classification model. This method showcases promising potential for early cervical cancer diagnosis, complementing conventional histopathological techniques.

These findings unveil the potential of vibrational spectroscopy, particularly FTIR microspectroscopy, for an early diagnosis of cervical cancer, assisting conventional histopathological methods, which will ultimately improve chemotherapy outcomes and patient prognosis.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) within the scope of the Strategic Programme of the Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit UIDB/ 00070/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/00070/2020>) & UIDP/00070/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/00070/2020>), and the A.L.M.B.d.C. employment contract (<https://doi.org/10.54499/CEECIND/00069/2017/CP1460/CT0029>).

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FP3. INSIGHTS INTO THE EFFECT OF GLUCOSE ON THE BINDING BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND THE NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUG NIMESULIDE

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Keywords: *Albumin-Drug Interactions, Diabetes mellitus, Spectroscopy, Molecular Docking.*

ABSTRACT

Glucose interacts with human serum albumin (HSA, the main protein responsible for the biodistribution of drugs in the bloodstream) and consequently affects the binding capacity of exogenous compounds [1]. Thus, in this work, the interactive profile between HSA and the anti-inflammatory drug nimesulide (NMD, used mainly by patients with diabetic neuropathy to relieve acute or chronic pains) [2] was characterized in nonglycemic, normoglycemic (80 mg/dL), and hyperglycemic (320 mg/dL) conditions by biophysics techniques, e.g., UV-Vis absorption, steady-state fluorescence, time-resolved fluorescence, circular dichroism, and molecular docking calculations. There is a spontaneous and ground-state association HSA:NMD under physiological conditions [3]. Therefore, the Stern-Volmer constant (K_{sv}) can also be used to estimate the binding affinity [4]. The K_{sv} values for nonglycemic, normoglycemic, and hyperglycemic conditions are around 10^4 M^{-1} , indicating a moderate affinity of NMD to albumin [3,5] that was slightly improved by glucose levels. Additionally, the binding is enthalpically and entropically driven mainly into subdomains IIA or IIIA [1,3]. The binding perturbs weakly the α -helix content of albumin, however, glucose potentially stabilizes the tertiary structure, decreasing the structural perturbation upon NMD binding and improves the complex HSA:NMD stability. Overall, the biophysical characterization indicated that glucose levels might slightly positively impact the pharmacokinetic profile of NMD, allowing NMD to achieve its therapeutical potential without affecting drastically its effective dosages.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) through the projects from CQC: UIDB/00313/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/00313/2020>) and UIDP/00313/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/00313/2020>). O.A.C. also thanks FCT for his PhD fellowship 2020.07504.BD.

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FP4. LYOTROPIC LIQUID CRYSTALLINE NANOASSEMBLIES: ADVANCED MULTIFUNCTIONAL NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER TREATMENT

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Keywords: *Cancer, Conventional therapies, Drug-delivery systems, Lyotropic liquid crystalline (LLC) mesophases, Doxorubicin.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer remains a leading cause of mortality. Despite significant breakthroughs in conventional therapies, treatment remains far from ideal due to high toxicity and therapeutic inefficiency. Current research focuses on the development of multifunctional nanosystems for delivery of different therapeutic agents. Lyotropic liquid crystalline (LLC) mesophases have emerged as a promising class of advanced delivery systems due to the several advantages of highly curved nonlamellar lipid assemblies including a higher surface area to volume ratio. Furthermore, they present structures with variable membrane stress, which is useful for improving permeation and cell internalization.

Given their promising features, we developed and optimized LLC nanoassemblies by considering the different methods of preparation and loading with doxorubicin, as well as their colloidal stability, through comprehensive physicochemical characterization. In addition, we also evaluated the therapeutic efficacy of nanoassemblies by the kinetic drug release profiles, cytotoxicity studies and cellular uptake.

The developed LLC nanoassemblies had a size of less than 250 nm, a high drug encapsulation efficiency (>90%), and a high drug loading capacity (>7%) with a colloidal stability lasting at least 4 weeks. Moreover, the kinetic drug release profiles demonstrated that the produced LLC nanoassemblies reduce cytotoxicity in healthy cells, since the cubosomes showed a higher release of DOX under acidic conditions (pH 5.5, typical of tumor tissues) and a significantly lower release under normal physiological conditions (pH 7.5), which is consistent with cytotoxicity studies and cellular uptake. Overall, these findings suggest that therapeutic agents loaded into LLC nanoassemblies could offer superior improvements to conventional chemotherapy.

FP5. THE PUZZLING ARSENITE OXIDASE REACTION MECHANISM: PUTTING THE PIECES TOGETHER

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Keywords: Molybdenum-enzyme, arsenic, X-ray crystallography, NMR, microscale thermophoresis.

ABSTRACT

Water contamination with arsenic (As) presents a global threat both to the environment and to public health. A study published in Science (1) identified that up to 220 million people are at risk thanks to groundwater consumption that exceeds the recommended WHO maximum value of 10 µg/L for As (2). The arsenite oxidase (Aio) (3-5), a complex metalloenzyme, is a good candidate to be used as a biosensor and in remediation since it oxidizes arsenite (AsIII) and antimonite (SbIII)(6), to less toxic and easier to remove species (AsV/SbV). Our goal is to unravel Aio's catalytic mechanism and characterize its interaction with the electron acceptor partners – cytochrome c552 or azurin – paving the way to develop new bioengineered solutions simultaneously effective, clean, and economically sustainable(7). Only Aio's from *Pseudorhizobium banfieldiae* NT-26 (NT-26 Aio) and *Alcaligenes faecalis* (Af Aio) have had their X-ray structures determined (3-5); these correspond to ligand-free forms, revealing very little regarding the catalytic reaction. We obtained 4 high-resolution structures (up to 1.44 Å) for complexes of NT-26 and Af Aio with As/Sb oxyanions bound to the active site that allowed us to revisit the catalytic mechanism of AsIII oxidation(8). Additionally, we determined the K_d's of Aio with both physiological partners, using microscale thermophoresis. NMR spectroscopy allowed for the identification of the amino acids involved in electron transfer and interaction between Af Aio and azurin. Also, two mutants near the [2Fe-2S] centre were characterized, kinetically using UV-Vis spectroscopy, and structurally through X-ray crystallography, to unveil the role of the disulphide bridge in the interaction with electron acceptors.

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FP6. COMBINING COMPUTATIONAL AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS TO DEVELOP TAILOR-MADE BIOPHARMACEUTICALS TARGETING INFLUENZA A HEMAGGLUTININ

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Keywords: *Hemagglutinin, monobody, computational methods, confidence metrics, MD simulations*

ABSTRACT

The emergence of viral pandemics highlights the need for preparedness. Influenza, a virus with high pandemic potential, relies on hemagglutinin (HA) to invade host cells. HA is a homotrimeric glycoprotein that promotes fusion of viral and host endosome membranes, making it a privileged target for antivirals. This project aims to design Virus-Targeting Antibody-like scaffolds (ViTAls), capable of binding to HA and blocking influenza virus entry.

ViTAls are designed using innovative computational methods. The strategy uses a monobody as a scaffold that offers adaptable loops for target interaction. Firstly, loops of a previously characterized neutralizing antibody were grafted onto the monobody, and the structure was predicted with AlphaFold2. The conformational dynamics and stability of this construct were studied with molecular dynamic (MD) simulations. The monobody conformations were docked onto the epitope with MaSIF¹, a deep-learning method based on geometrical and chemical features. ProteinMPNN², a deep learning-based sequence method, was used to re-design the sequence and enhance binding affinity. The designs were selected by confidence metrics using AlphaFold2^{3,4} and Rosetta Interface Analysis.

Some designs showed promising confidence metrics scores, including shape complementarity, interface-predicted template modeling score, and unsatisfied hydrogen bonds in the interface. These designs were then subjected to MD simulations to analyze their stability. Candidates passing computational filters are then produced in bacteria and characterized by assessing folding and thermal stability, as well as aggregation propensity. This work contributes to developing and validating an innovative strategy that can be applied to tackle various viruses, including influenza A.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia and LaCaixa Foundation under the project "The BioPlaTTAR Platform for the Tailored and Rapid Development of Antiviral Biopharmaceuticals," along with additional grants from iBET, Instruct, and EvaMobs.

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FP7. COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF NOVEL ANTIVIRALS THAT TARGET THE ZIKA VIRUS ENVELOPE PROTEIN DOMAIN III

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Keywords: *Zika virus, Monobodies, ProteinMPNN, AlphaFold2, Molecular dynamics.*

ABSTRACT

In the past two decades, the world has struggled with recurrent viral outbreaks, with viruses from diverse families demonstrating pandemic and epidemic potential. One of those viruses is the Zika virus. In the Zika virus, the envelope protein (E) has a pivotal role in viral entry into host cells. It comprises three structural ectodomains (DI, DII, DIII) and a transmembrane region. DIII is an immunoglobulin-like domain that contains receptor-binding sites. Protein design has emerged as a powerful tool for customizing protein properties like stability and binding affinity. In this work, we are designing monobodies, small proteins derived from the human FN3 domain, that target the Zika virus E protein DIII.

Epitope regions on the target surface were identified and state-of-the-art protein design tools, such as ProteinMPNN[1], were used to increase the binding affinity of monobodies to the target. Protein structure prediction tools, like AlphaFold2[2][3] and Rosetta[4], were used to filter the most promising designs. Molecular dynamics simulations were conducted to assess the stability of both the top-scoring design and the target structure (DIII).

A total of 15 designs passed the AlphaFold2 ($i_pTM > 0.6$) and Rosetta (shape complementarity, buns2 and ddG) filters. The top-scoring design presented an i_pTM value over 0.7. Molecular dynamics simulations show that DIII is quite stable on its own. Innovative design strategies are being tested at the moment with very promising results.

This comprehensive approach seeks to redefine strategies in combating the Zika virus, holding the potential to enhance preparedness against emerging viral threats.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by LaCaixa Foundation, within the projects “The BioPlATTAR Platform for the Tailored and Rapid Development of Antiviral Biopharmaceuticals” and “EvaMobs, a Horizon Europe Framework Programme, under reference HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03-04, ID 101137419”, and by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (iNOVA4Health: UIDB/04462/2020, MostMicro: UIDP/04612/2020, LS4Future: LA/P/0087/2020).

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FP8. COMPUTATIONAL EVIDENCES OF A MISFOLDING EVENT IN AN AGGREGATION-PRONE LIGHT CHAIN PRECEDING THE FORMATION OF THE NON-NATIVE PATHOGENIC DIMER.

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Keywords: AL amyloidosis, *misfolding*, *Molecular Dynamics*, *pathogenic dimer*.

ABSTRACT

Antibody light chain amyloidosis is a condition due to the aggregation and deposition of immunoglobulin light chains in diverse tissues resulting in organ impairment[1]. The high susceptibility of antibodies to mutations makes AL amyloidosis strongly patient-specific. In this context, understanding the processes underlying fibrillization is crucial in the perspective of achieving prompt diagnoses and designing personalized therapeutics. Here, we focus on a particular patient-derived light chain, previously experimentally characterized[2].

We investigated the early phases of the aggregation pathway through extensive full-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, on the germ-line non-aggregating monomer and on its mutant aggregation-prone counterpart. Next, we moved to consider the dimerization process through docking and MD simulations, proposing a pathological dimeric structure.

The simulations on the monomers revealed significant changes in the mutant light chain structure with the exposure of two previously buried hydrophobic residues. Based on this evidence we speculated that these could be part of a binding region leading to pathogenic dimerization. MD simulations on the docked structures allowed to find the most stable putative pathogenic dimer.

The results obtained could pave the way to the computational study of ensuing phases of light chain aggregation (e.g. involving coarse-grained simulations to observe oligomerization). Furthermore, extending the methods employed to other cases of aggregating light chains could uncover some common mechanisms driving misfolding and initial pathological association in AL amyloidosis. This could lead to the development of patient-specific drugs able to hinder protein assembly in the earliest stages.

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FP9. EXPLORING EARLY-ON PROTONATION DYNAMICS ASSOCIATED WITH THE (DE)ACTIVATION OF CLASS A GPCRS

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Keywords: *Constant pH Molecular Dynamics, Protonation, pKa Calculations.*

ABSTRACT

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) are the therapeutic targets for ~35% of the currently available pharmaceutical drugs. Recent studies suggest that class A GPCRs share a common (de)activation pathway with discernible changes in the network of residue contacts [1]. The protonation state of key residues, such as Asp2.50, can act as a microswitch for this mechanism, albeit the dynamics of this process remain incompletely elucidated [2].

Employing CHARMM36m Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations (100 ns), we explored both active and inactive initial conformations of five different class A GPCR systems, with a protonated and deprotonated Asp2.50. Throughout the simulations, pK_a calculations were performed using PypKa. The resulting data was used with a Linear Response Approximation method to estimate macroscopic pK_a values for the active and inactive conformations for each system.

Our results show a difference of 1.3 pK_a units between active and inactive states for non-constitutive GPCRs, but inconsistent differences for constitutive GPCRs, ranging from -0.3 to 0.3 pK_a units. We were also able to detect a possible early-stage (de)activation event associated with the suggested Asp2.50 function as a microswitch.

Our protocol offers insights into protonation preferences of active and inactive states of these class A GPCRs, and early-on (de)activation dynamics that might occur in this process, particularly in non-constitutive GPCRs. This is an important step towards understanding disease-causing mutations and dysfunctions, potentially paving the way for the development of novel therapies.

Acknowledgements: Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, for grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and 2022.11124.BD and projects UIDB/04046/2020 and UIDP/04046/2020. Funded by the European Union (TWIN2PIPSA, GA 101079147).

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FP10. REVOLUTIONIZING ALZHEIMER'S TREATMENT: HARNESSING PHOTOSWITCHABLE MOLECULES THROUGH CUTTING-EDGE *IN SILICO* METHODS IN NEUROSCIENCE

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Keywords: *Alzheimer, Small Molecules, Photoswitchable, Cheminformatics, Orexin Receptors.*

Alzheimer's disease is characterized by a progressive decline in memory and cognitive abilities¹. In 2021, the FDA approved aducanumab as the first Amyloid-targeting monoclonal antibody. However, its effectiveness and safety remain under scrutiny². This underscores the urgent need for the development of new drugs and treatments. Recent, research suggests a potential link between Alzheimer's disease and the orexinergic system, which is crucial in regulating the sleep-wake cycle³.

Our approach involved developing and optimizing a chemical library of photoswitchable small molecules targeting the orexin receptors, using ligand structure-based drug design techniques. We used ChEMBL Database to identify and extract compounds targeting orexin receptor types 1 and 2, and the ZINC Database to find and extract compounds with an azobenzene structure. Hierarchical clustering was applied to discover meaningful scaffolds within the data. Additionally, azobenzene compounds were docked in both cis and trans conformations, with their interactions being analyzed.

The chemical space analysis revealed that some azobenzene compounds exhibit structural similarities with compounds from the ChEMBL database targeting both orexin receptors. Hierarchical clustering successfully identified meaningful scaffolds associated with activity. The analysis of protein-ligand interactions revealed differences in binding between the cis and trans conformers, highlighting strong interaction similarities with the protein, particularly at the α PHE-219 residue.

The chemical library of photoswitchable small molecules targeting the orexin receptors developed in this study shows promise for providing novel therapeutic avenues in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by HEU Project Tclock4AD GA number 101072895, EXPL/QUI-OUT/1288/2021, UIDB/04138/2020, UIDP/04138/2020, and COMPETE LISBOA-01-0246-FEDER-000017.

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FP11. STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTION OF A HUMAN MOLECULAR MACHINE: THE RUVBL1/RUVBL2 COMPLEX AND THEIR ROLE IN PAQOSOME

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Keywords: *Interactome, ATPases, RuvBL1 /RuvBL2*

ABSTRACT

RuvBL1/RuvBL2 are AAA+ ATPases known to participate in large molecular complexes such as INO80, TIP60 or R2TP, and have been associated with many cellular functions including chromatin remodelling, transcription, and apoptosis, suggesting that they could act as a scaffolding complex. In addition, a link between RuvBLs and cancer was established as they interact with transcription regulators known to be involved in oncogenic pathways and are overexpressed in many cancer types. However, little is known about the disease-related molecular mechanisms.

This PhD project aimed to identify partners and client proteins of RuvBL1/2 in the context of large complexes. We focused on understanding how they assemble and their overall architecture, all with an eye towards exploring their potential for drug development. We implemented an innovative enzyme-catalyzed proximity labeling method, termed TurboID, which enabled us to explore the interactome of RuvBLs within their natural cellular environment, identifying their associated partners and client proteins. We successfully detected certain proteins known to be part of the macromolecular complex PAQosome and involved in the snoRNPs biogenesis, with statistically relevant confidence. To validate their interactions, we employed SPR using our newly developed Extract2Chip methodology. This approach avoids the need for protein purification by utilizing cell lysates enriched in biotinylated targets, allowing us to kinetically characterize their interactions with protein partners or small molecules through SPR. In addition, we conducted comprehensive biochemical-, biophysical- and structural analyses.

This approach enabled us to correlate 3D-structures with functional studies, shedding light on the assembly mechanisms and functions of these molecular machines.

FP12. DESIGNING THE FUTURE OF CANCER IMMUNOTHERAPY: A COMPUTATIONAL STRATEGY FOR DUAL INHIBITION OF TIGIT AND PD-L1 PROTEINS

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Keywords: *Cancer Therapy, Dual Inhibitor, PD-L1, Small Molecule, TIGIT*

ABSTRACT

TIGIT and PD-L1 are frequently overexpressed in cancer patients and are known to suppress the immune system response by inhibiting the ability of T and NK cells to eliminate cancer cells^{1,2}. Given their critical roles in immune evasion by tumors, the development of a dual inhibitor represents a crucial strategy in cancer therapy.

Utilizing a structure-based approach, we conducted a comparative analysis of the binding pockets of TIGIT and PD-L1. Alignment was performed using TM-align, PyMOL, and PocketAlign, while their chemical properties were assessed using MOE. Additionally, the similarity between the two pockets was examined using PocketMatch^{3,4}. Focusing on TIGIT, we constructed a homology model using Modeller, which was posteriorly validated. Moreover, the dynamics of TIGIT's binding pocket was investigated through AA-MD simulations.

Analysis revealed that TIGIT's pocket exhibits significantly higher hydrophobicity compared to that of PD-L1. However, PocketMatch identified a similarity score of 68% between the two pockets and an aligned region of 6-to-17 residues was observed. Plus, AA-MD simulations unveiled that TYR-113 within TIGIT's pocket alternates between two different conformations: open and closed.

Our research establishes a solid foundation for developing a pharmacophore model targeting the aligned region. However, the dynamic nature of TIGIT's binding pocket may pose challenges in creating a robust homology model, which is essential for the effective virtual screening of extensive databases and compounds identified through Machine Learning methods. In pursuit of discovering a molecule that inhibits both proteins, we are currently evaluating different docking softwares to determine which most accurately predicts biological activity.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT): under grant 2023.01201.BD. The authors acknowledge the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia for the financial support under the grants UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed. RCG acknowledges funding from LISBOA-01-0246-FEDER-000017, funded by FEDER through COMPETE2020.

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FP13. DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF A MULTI-LEVEL COMPUTATIONAL AND IN VITRO APPROACH FOR IDENTIFYING MAPK3 INHIBITORS IN *LEISHMANIA MARTINIQUENSIS* AND *LEISHMANIA ORIENTALIS*

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Keywords: *MAPK3 protein, Molecular dynamics simulations, Molecular docking, Homology modelling, structure-based virtual screening*

ABSTRACT

Leishmania martiniquensis and *Leishmania orientalis* are two major species of parasites associated with health problems in Thailand. The MAPK3 protein plays a crucial role in disease transmission. Therefore, the current work focuses on identifying tripeptides as potent molecular inhibitors targeting the MAPK3 proteins of these two species.

This study describes a multi-level *in silico* method (including homology modeling, molecular dynamics simulations, and molecular docking) and an *in vitro* method targeting MAPK3 for discovering new MAPK3 inhibitors with high potency among 8,000 linear tripeptides.

From an initial library of 8,000 tripeptides, 10 peptides were chosen through virtual screening. These were then used for MD simulations to evaluate their potential binding with MAPK3 kinase. The results indicated that four peptides displayed significantly higher binding energies across all targets. Among the four tripeptides tested, the WSY tripeptide exhibited significantly higher effectiveness in inhibiting MAPK3 at a concentration of 3.33 μ M, with a percentage inhibition of 89.97 \pm 9.28%.

This study optimized an *in silico* and *in vitro* protocol to identify potent molecular inhibitors targeting Leishmaniasis sp. MAPK3, with peptide WSY showing promise in inhibiting LdMAPK3, LmrMAPK3, and LoMAPK3, suggesting potential for future therapeutic development.

Acknowledgements: FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020) (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020 and UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020)

FP14. FROM IN SILICO TO THE WET LAB: PAVING THE WAY IN LCP FAMILY INHIBITION

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Keywords: *Bacteria, Biofilms, WTAs, LCP*

Abstract

Cell wall glycopolymers (CWGPs) are essential constituents of the cell wall in gram-positive bacteria and play a key role in bacterial survival and/or pathogenesis. By depleting bacteria of CWGPs, their growth and division can be hampered, increasing their susceptibility to antibiotic treatment and facilitating the fight against infections. The biosynthesis pathway for all CWGPs is very complex, but the final step, that consists in the transference from the lipidic precursor into the peptidoglycan, takes place outside the cell and is mediated by the LytR-CpsA-Psr (LCP) family of proteins, making this family a target for therapeutic intervention. These proteins are known to be pyrophosphatases and recently we were able to prove that these family of proteins can hydrolyze ADP to AMP.

In this work the LytR protein, from *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* subsp. *dysgalactiae* (SDSD) were analyzed. LytR was structurally characterized by X-ray Crystallography. From the experimental determined structure we performed molecular dynamics (MD) and virtual screening (VS) to search for interacting compounds.

It was possible to obtain a crystal structure of the LytR protein at 2.80 Å resolution. From the virtual screening 10 promising molecules were obtained. Followed by a 600 ns MD where the compounds remained bound to the protein and molecular mechanics with generalised Born and surface area solvation (MM/GBSA) calculations values consistent with interaction with the protein.

The VS was an important tool in finding promising molecules that are currently being tested experimentally using thermal shift assay (TSA) and NMR.

FP15. TARGETING THE CIRCADIAN CLOCK AND ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A STRUCTURE-BASED STRATEGY TO DISCOVER OREXIN RECEPTOR PHOTOSWITCHES

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Keywords: *Orexin receptors, Alzheimer's disease, Photoswitches, Docking, Receptor-ligand interactions*

ABSTRACT

Recent research suggests a link between dysfunction in the orexinergic system and cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease (AD), spotlighting orexin receptors 1 and 2 (OX₁R and OX₂R) as potential targets for AD research and therapeutic intervention. This study aims to establish a computational protocol that can successfully identify OX₁R antagonists, to inform the synthesis of photoswitchable antagonists for this receptor. Photoswitchable ligands are known for their ability to undergo reversible and controlled conformational changes upon light exposure, altering their affinity, potency, or other pharmacodynamic properties. Such capability offers precise spatial and temporal regulation of orexin receptor activation *in vivo*, crucial for investigating and pharmacologically targeting the orexin system' in AD.

All ligands targeting OX₁R with available K_i data were retrieved from ChEMBL (current release: ChEMBL 33), and filtered to eliminate duplicates, compounds exceeding a molecular weight of 700 Da, and assays with low confidence scores. The choice of the OX₁R structure (PDB ID: 6TQ4), featuring three conserved water molecules, was chosen based on previous cross-docking studies. Ligand and receptor structures were prepared using MOE (v.2020.0901). Docking was carried out using Smina software (v.2019-10-15), selecting the top pose based on docking scores. Interaction analyses between receptor and ligands were calculated using PLIP (v.2.3.0).

Our analysis revealed a correlation between Smina docking scores and K_i values, even after normalization for the molecules' number of heavy atoms. Additionally, we identified specific interaction patterns (signatures) that typify effective antagonists.

The integration of Smina docking scores with identified interaction signatures presents a promising approach for efficient virtual screening of photoswitchable antagonists targeting orexin receptor. This method holds potential for advancing the discovery of novel therapeutics in Alzheimer's disease by enabling the precision-targeted modulation of the orexin system.

FP16. BIOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF AGING NUCLEAR MEMBRANES: IMPLICATIONS FROM MODEL SYSTEMS

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Keywords: *aging, nucleus, lamins, membrane biophysics, fluorescence*

ABSTRACT

Aging is a major risk factor for various diseases, yet understanding of cellular aging is incomplete. Many aging-related changes emerge in the nucleus. Recently, altered cell mechanical properties have become a hallmark of aging, with the nuclear envelope (NE) and lamins playing a pivotal role in maintaining nuclear integrity. Although the interplay between NE and lamina during aging is not fully understood, we hypothesize that the lipidome of the NE influences lamin binding and organization. Our preliminary lipidomics findings indicate a decline in ether lipids with age progression. This might impact the biophysical properties of membranes and lead to differential lamin binding. Thus, we propose to create age-tuned synthetic models to investigate nuclear aging, NE-lamin interactions, and overall nuclear structural integrity.

We designed membrane models mimicking the NE of both young and old healthy donors with distinct ether lipid content. To characterize membrane properties, we performed DPH fluorescence anisotropy measurements, Laurdan generalized polarization (GP), and time-dependent fluorescence shifts (TDFS).

Decrease in ether lipid content does not alter the hydrophobic core of the membrane but makes it more ordered closer to the surface. TDFS results reveal that membrane order changes due to viscosity and mobility, but not polarity and hydration. Such organization of the membrane can significantly impact how lamins interact with the models.

These findings serve as a foundation for upcoming experiments, and incorporation of key lamina proteins into nucleus-sized models will provide new insights into protein-lipid interactions during healthy human aging.

FP17. MOLECULAR RECOGNITION OF MULTIVALENT GLYCOMIMETICS BY HUMAN MACROPHAGE GALACTOSE-TYPE LECTIN

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Keywords: *Molecular Recognition, NMR, MGL, Glycomimetics, cancer.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer cells overexpress tumour-associated *O*-glycans that interact with immune lectins leading to antitumour immune suppression. In this context, the macrophage galactose-type lectin (MGL) is expressed in macrophages and dendritic cells and recognizes GalNAc-containing antigens inducing immune suppressive responses. The rational design of molecules to block these aberrant interactions is an attractive strategy for the development of novel immunotherapies. Since monovalent glycan-protein interactions are usually weak, nature compensates for this phenomenon by multivalent interactions. In this communication the molecular recognition of monomeric and trimeric glycomimetics containing GalNAc and Deoxy-Gal-GalNAc motifs by MGL, will be described. ¹H,¹⁵N-HSQC based titrations, diffusion experiments and ITC measurements were performed and integrated with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, using methodologies optimized in the group. The results showed an increase in the avidity of the complexes upon multivalent presentation and illustrated that more than one MGL domain interacts with the trimeric glycomimetics simultaneously. In conclusion, multivalency is an important feature when designing molecules to block interactions.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: MGL4Life DOI 10.54499/PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020, UCIBIO project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 and Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020). F.M. thank FCT-Portugal for the CEEC Institutional contract CEECINST/00042/2021. C.L. acknowledge the PhD grant 2021.06789.BD. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013- PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). F.M. and C.G. acknowledge the COST Action GLYCONanoProbes (CA18132). F.M. and J.J.B acknowledge EU funding for the GLYCOTwinning project.

FP18. UNVEILING DRUG-LIPID INTERACTIONS: A SYNCHROTRON-BASED FTIR STUDY

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Keywords: *Vibrational Spectroscopy, Lipids, Metallodrugs, Synchrotron Radiation, Intermolecular Interactions.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer is well known as one of the most prominent causes of death worldwide, with new and improved chemotherapeutic strategies standing as a clinical need. The urgency in finding new solutions towards solving this problem led to a plethora of research efforts, among which liposome encapsulated metal chelates can be highlighted.[1,2] Despite their potential as anticancer formulations, the interplay between these drugs and liposome membranes is still undisclosed, being the main focus of this research.

Spectra were obtained in the far (HE-cooled bolometer/Si beamsplitter) and mid-infrared (MCT detector/KBr beamsplitter) regions. 512 co-added scans were acquired for FIR and MIR, at 2 cm⁻¹ spectral resolution. A background was taken at each 6 measurements (from the empty ATR diamond crystal). A polyethylene holder was used to accommodate the samples on the ATR module.

The impact of platinum and palladium metallodrugs on the structural behavior of lipidic membranes was successfully analyzed using model lipids – phosphatidylcholine and phosphoethanolamine derivatives, glycolipids and cholesterol. The dinuclear palladium complex Pd₂Spm (Spm=Spermine=H₂N(CH₂)₃NH(CH₂)₄NH(CH₂)₃NH₂) was assessed,[3] as well as cisplatin as a reference drug, revealing structural changes on the adducts induced by the establishment of intermolecular interactions, identified by notable shifts on key vibrational modes.

Using a synchrotron-based vibrational spectroscopic method allowed to determine the impact of platinum and palladium metallodrugs on the behavior of lipidic adducts. Although additional data is needed to confirm this findings, valuable knowledge on drug-lipid interactions was achieved, providing valuable inputs on the development of new and viable drug delivery systems.

Acknowledgements: QFM-UC is supported by national funds through FCT – Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P., under the project UIDB/00070/2020. J.A.V.S. acknowledge FCT (grant UIDB/00070/2020) for financial support. Thanks are due to Diamond Light Source, for providing the SR-FTIR-ATR facilities.

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FP19. TOXICITY ASSESSMENT OF THE PHOTOCATALYTIC PROCESS USING FERRITE NANOMATERIALS $Zn_{0.5}X_{0.5}Fe_2O_4$ (X=Mg, Cu): INSIGHTS FROM *VIBRIO FISCHERI* ON POLLUTANT REMOVAL EFFICIENCY

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Keywords: *Nanomaterials, Photocatalysis, Toxicity.*

ABSTRACT

The escalating threat of anthropogenic pollutants is currently affecting water resources and, consequently, impacting ecosystems and public health. The imperative for developing new treatment processes to supplant or augment existing ones in Wastewater treatment plants emerges as an urgent contemporary necessity.

Photocatalysis assisted by nanomaterials is an efficient process on degrading highly complex pollutants such as dyes and pharmaceuticals, breaking the chemical structure of the pollutant into less complex species. Although the final aim is their mineralization into inert species such as CO₂ and H₂O, this is often not the case. So, evaluating the toxicity of by-products is crucial.

Vibrio fischeri is used as a toxicity biosensor due to its sensitivity and the possibility of performing easy and short-term assays [1, 2]. In this study, the toxicity associated to the photocatalytic degradation of the model pollutant Malachite Green (MG) was assessed. Two different nanomaterials were tested: Ag@Zn_{0.5}Mg_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ and Ag@Zn_{0.5}Cu_{0.5}Fe₂O₄. The results demonstrated an increase in toxicity after the photocatalytic treatment suggesting the formation of intermediates of the reaction more toxic than the pollutant itself.

A vast majority of research studies proposing degradation treatments, whether biological or chemical, focuses on the removal of the initial compounds (usually a model compound) not taking into account the possible toxicity of the products formed after degradation, nor the catalysts themselves. Toxicological and environmental impact assessment is an important issue that must be considered when proposing degradation processes and when nanomaterials are applied.

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FP20. SHINING INSIGHT: PROBING LUNG CANCER CELLS WITH A NON-CONVENTIONAL PLATINUM COMPLEX

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ABSTRACT

Following cardiovascular diseases, cancer is the second cause of death worldwide, lung cancer having the highest mortality rate, mostly due to the late diagnosis. Chemotherapy, through cisplatin administration combined with a third-generation drug, is currently the standard treatment. However, it is associated to severe deleterious side effects. Thus, it is imperative to develop potential new drugs with enhanced antitumor activity while minimizing toxicity. Particularly regarding metal-based anticancer agents, biogenic polyamines have been considered as suitable biocompatible ligands. Given their amphipathic properties and high flexibility, not only the cellular uptake of the complexes may be enhanced but also their interaction with DNA and other biomolecules which can act as therapeutic targets. Furthermore, polyamine chelates with more than one metal centre allow the formation of long range and interstrand adducts within DNA, not available to conventional metal drugs such as cisplatin.

The present study focused on the synthesis and biological activity of a complex comprising two Pt(II) centers and two bridging putrescine molecules ($H_2N(CH_2)_4NH_2$). In vitro screening assays (*e.g.* MTT and SRB) were performed in human lung cancer cells, and in non-malignant human lung cells. Vibrational microspectroscopy – microFTIR and microRaman – was then applied to evaluate the compound's effect on the cellular metabolic profile. The spectral data was analyzed by to Principal Components Analysis (PCA), revealing a major impact on proteins, as compared to the other major cellular constituents (nucleic acids, carbohydrates and lipids).

These are very promising results, which are expected to contribute for a more successful management of human lung cancer.

POSTER SESSION

Abstracts

P1. DUPLEX-QUADRUPLEX COMPETITION AT PROMOTERS

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Keywords: *quadruplexes, promoters, transcription, competition assay*

ABSTRACT

G-quadruplexes (G4) are secondary structures formed by guanine-rich DNA or RNA. Four guanines associate via intra-quartet Hydrogen bonds, to form highly polymorphic G4 structures, stabilized by cations. In the context of single-stranded DNA, quadruplexes are well characterized *in vitro* under near-physiological conditions. At the transcriptional level, Jean-Christophe Andrau and co-workers have shown that quadruplexes are core elements of the transcription machinery, where the G4 would have to form in dsDNA, which to our knowledge, has not been investigated in detail for long sequences.

In this study, we wanted to study *in vitro* the competition between quadruplexes and duplexes. To do so, we selected promoters sequences and developed biophysical assays to show whether a G4 is forming in long dsDNA. We tested different annealing protocols to study this competition, either by mixing the two strands before or after annealing.

We found that the duplex-quadruplex competition depended on primary sequence, annealing conditions and length of the complementary strands. Quadruplex may still form in the presence of its complementary strand when the strands are mixed *after* annealing. In contrast, half of the promoters can form G4 in dsDNA when the two strands are mixed before annealing.

To answer a relevant question in the G4 community regarding quadruplex formation in the context of dsDNA, we developed some tools to study duplex/quadruplex competition. The results were very promising as we were able to show that G4 formation is still possible in the presence of the complementary strand and in absence of stabilizing factors.

P2. IMPROVING THE BACMAM SYSTEM FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF AMPA RECEPTOR COMPLEXES

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Keywords: *Structure, protein expression, BacMam, membrane proteins.*

ABSTRACT

Structural characterization of eukaryotic membrane proteins is challenging due to their hydrophobic nature, reliance on a near-native environment for structural integrity and low protein yields. Transient and stable transfection and viral delivery are the most frequently used methods for gene delivery into mammalian cells. Baculovirus-mediated delivery (BacMam) is particularly useful as it relies on insect cell viruses which do not replicate in mammalian cells. Here we modified the BacMam plasmids and protocols for high-yield membrane protein production. We applied the method to study the AMPA glutamate receptor assembly pathway, where three membrane proteins (ABHD6, CPT1c and FRRS1L) regulate receptor oligomerization.

We used IVA cloning to introduce two fluorescent tags into a BacMam plasmid under the control of a polyhedrin promoter and generated a library of baculoviruses encoding AMPARs (GluA1-4) and partners. We transduced viruses into HEK cells grown in suspension and we purified complexes by immunoaffinity purification followed by size exclusion chromatography. We used negative staining electron microscopy to analyze the complexes.

pBicMam-green and pBicMam-red plasmids enable successful virus generation and provide high AMPAR complexes yields in HEK cells. As previously reported, GluA subunits interact with ABHD6 and FRRS1L-CPT1c complexes. ABHD6 prevents AMPAR oligomerization and the complex can be purified at high yields. Negative staining analysis suggest that the complex is highly flexible.

Baculoviruses generated with pBicMam plasmids are purified at high titers and they efficiently transduce mammalian cells. They can be efficiently used to produce different AMPA receptor complexes for structural analysis by cryo-EM.

P3. MOLECULAR INSIGHTS INTO THE BIOGENESIS OF BOX H/ACA snoRNPS

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Keywords: *Cryo-EM, RuvBL1/2, SPR, XL-MS, Mass-Photometry.*

ABSTRACT

Guided by the RNA component, box H/ACA snoRNPs find their target RNAs and convert the nuclear base uridine to pseudouridine, resulting in increased stability of the target RNA. Pseudouridines are vital for various cellular functions, such as protein translation, as they undergo frequent post-transcriptional modifications in ribosomal RNAs.

However, it is still poorly understood how these complexes and their individual protein precursors are assembled. SHQ1 is proposed to prevent DKC1 from binding to nonspecific ribonucleases during its assembly in the cytosol and subsequently guide the complex to the nucleus, where it interacts with the AAA-ATPase complex RuvBL1/2. These ATPases are known to interact with PIH1D1 and RPAP3 proteins to form the R2TP complex, which is described to play a role in the assembly of multiple macromolecular complexes. Thus, the R2TP complex could be responsible for sequestering SHQ1 from DKC1, allowing DKC1 to interact with Box H/ACA snoRNAs and ultimately assemble the mature snoRNP.

The aim of this work is to elucidate the maturation of Box H/ACA snoRNPS by characterizing precursor complexes composed of SHQ1, DKC1, and RuvBL1/2. This was achieved using size exclusion chromatography, dynamic light scattering, differential scanning fluorimetry, surface plasmon resonance, mass photometry, cross-linking mass spectrometry, and cryo-EM

We were able to confirm the interaction between RuvBL1/2 and DKC1 or SHQ1. Additionally, we purified and stabilized SHQ1:RuvBL1/2 complexes and identified multiple complex species. Revealing the interaction site between the AAA ATPases and SHQ1 led to the initial 3D reconstruction of the complex's structure using Cryo-EM.

P4. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO PROMISCUOUS GPCR-G PROTEIN COUPLING

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Keywords: *GPCR, G protein, promiscuous coupling, Cryo-EM*

ABSTRACT

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) constitute the largest family of membrane receptors and detect extracellular signals to transduce them across biological membranes by activating heterotrimeric $G\alpha\beta\gamma$ proteins. There are 16 human $G\alpha$ proteins classified into four families (G_s , $G_{i/o}$, $G_{q/11}$, and $G_{12/13}$), each initiating distinct signaling cascades. GPCRs generally activate multiple types of $G\alpha$ proteins generating a fingerprint-like signaling profile. This work aims to unravel the molecular mechanisms that support de selectivity between GPCR and G proteins.

We have use structural analysis of seven cryo-EM structures of GPCRs coupled to different $G\alpha$ proteins aiming to find structural coupling patterns. Additionally, we studied the G_o/G_i coupling preference of the Dopamine 3 Receptor (D_3R) using cryo-EM, site-directed mutagenesis and cellular signaling assays.

Previously, distinct coupling modes were seen for GPCRs coupling to G_s , $G_{i/o}$ or G_q with differences at the TM6 outward movement and intracellular loops interactions. In this work we observe that the extent of outward movement of TM6, persists when the receptor couples with different $G\alpha$ proteins, where the conformation used for their primary coupling prevails. Secondary $G\alpha$ couplings are differentiated by distinct interactions with intracellular loops. Finally, structural and functional analysis reveal the key G_o vs G_i selectivity players in D_3R .

This study has contributed to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying promiscuity between GPCRs and G proteins from different families, as well as the promiscuity within the same $G\alpha$ family.

Acknowledgements: We thank MICINN grant PID2020-113359GA-I00

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P5. A NEW ANTIVIRAL STRATEGY AGAINST PANDEMIC AND SEASONAL INFLUENZA A VIRUS

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Keywords: *Influenza virus, H1N1, Pandemics, Antiviral.*

ABSTRACT

Several pandemics have marked the past century. The 1918 pandemic caused by influenza A (INFA) virus subtype H1N1 stands out as one of the deadliest in history. The threat of the (re)emergence of pandemic viruses makes the discovery of new drugs imperative. The objective of this study is to investigate a novel category of small molecules with the potential to act as antiviral agents targeting INFA virus subtype H1N1, with the potential to broaden their spectrum of efficacy to other viruses with similar replication mechanisms.

The maximum non-cytotoxic concentrations of the compounds that can be used in the viral host cell line (MDCK CCI-34) and human lung epithelial cells (Calu-3 HTB-55) were determined by flow cytometry. Subsequently, with the execution of plaque assays, the antiviral activity of these compounds was preliminarily assessed. Hereafter, a biophysical characterization of the lead compounds will be performed by confocal and multiphoton microscopy, along with spectroscopy-based tests, to scrutinize their antiviral mechanism of action at the molecular level.

Preliminary data demonstrate that these compounds have antiviral properties against INFA virus, some showing a higher reduction in infectious virus particles when administered prophylactically (52.9% ± 12.0%), while other had a higher effect on the reduction when applied therapeutically (84.6% ± 11.6%).

Our work indicates that these molecules can effectively inhibit INFA virus *in vitro*. Further assessments are being carried out to thoroughly evaluate the activity of these molecules and their potential contribution to preparing a global and efficient response in future pandemic outbreaks.

P6. UNRAVELING THE MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF CATIONIC PEPTIDE DENDRIMERS AS PH-DEPENDENT VECTORS: AN *IN SILICO* APPROACH

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Keywords: CpHMD, pH, peptide dendrimers

ABSTRACT

Transfection is a pivotal process in both the industry and therapeutic fields, however, most transfection processes exhibit problems regarding cytotoxicity and immunogenicity¹. Recently, researchers have explored the use of peptide dendrimers as vectors for siRNA molecules². When composed of cationic and hydrophobic amino acid residues, such as lysines and leucines, these branched molecules interact strongly with nucleic acids, namely siRNA, and biological membranes². Their different protonation states at physiological and low pH values play a crucial role in interacting with negatively charged nucleic acids and escaping endosomal entrapment. Despite numerous experimental results, our understanding of the overall molecular mechanisms governing specific properties of these molecules still needs improving³.

In this study, we present our findings on the application of our advanced CpHMD methodology to investigate the pH-dependent conformational space of some of these peptide dendrimers. We performed the simulations in the aqueous phase, and in interaction with a lipid bilayer to assess how conformation and protonation are affected by pH in different environments. We found that these molecules become highly charged upon acidification, and a high charge density is essential to trigger membrane destabilization. These findings are in excellent agreement with the experimental data and help explain why some dendrimers are unable to undergo efficient endosome evasion and complete the transfection process. This evidence provides further understanding of the mode of action of these peptide dendrimers and will be vital for the future design of new sequences with improved transfection capabilities.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) for funding through projects UIDB/04046/2020 & UIDP/04046/2020 and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and 2021.05909.BD.

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P7. PROPERTIES AND INTERACTION OF HOECHST 33342 WITH POPC MEMBRANES

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Keywords: *biomembranes, fluorescent probe, membrane partition, pK_a , molecular dynamics simulations*

ABSTRACT

The fluorescent probe H33342 possesses 5 ionizing groups and is commonly used to stain the DNA of living cells. To accomplish this, it needs to interact with and permeate through cell membranes, despite its high overall charge at physiological pH values. The aim of this work is to evaluate H33342 properties and better understand the mechanisms of interaction of this probe with lipidic membranes.

H33342 acid-base properties were assessed by absorbance and fluorescence spectroscopy. The effect of pH in the association of H33342 with lipid bilayers were measured using a combined experimental and computational approach. The partition of H33342 to POPC lipid membranes was quantified using fluorescence spectroscopy and isothermal titration calorimetry measurements. Interaction of the most stable isomer with POPC bilayers was studied by both unrestrained and umbrella sampling molecular dynamics simulations (MD).

Both experimental and computational results indicate that the partition coefficient of H33342 displays a small variation over a wide pH range, not exceeding one order of magnitude. The enthalpy variation upon partition to the membrane suggests efficient hydrogen bonding between the probe and the lipid, namely, for the +2 form, which was confirmed by MD. The relatively high lipophilicity of charged species contrasts with the decrease in their general hydrophobicity as estimated from octanol/water partition.¹

This work clearly shows that lipophilicity cannot be directly estimated from solute hydrophobicity ($\text{Log}P_{\text{oct}}$ and $\text{Log}D_{\text{oct}}$), highlighting the importance of considering acid-base properties and the association with lipid bilayers when predicting the affinity for biomembranes.

Acknowledgements: COMPETE2020, FCT (fellowship 2022.11593.BD, projects UIDB/00313/2020, UIDP/00313/2020, UIDB/50006/2020, and UIDP/50006/2020), CENTRO-04-3559-FSE-000162.

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P8. THE EFFECT OF SILICA COATED SUPERPARAMAGNETIC IRON OXIDE NANOPARTICLES ON COLD PLASMA TREATED SKIN CANCER CELL LINES

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Keywords: *Cold atmospheric plasma - CAP, skin cancer, SPIONs, mesoporous silica*

ABSTRACT

Recent strides in cancer treatment have emphasized the pivotal role of combination therapies. Cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) has garnered considerable attention for its potential in treatment modalities. Our study aims at investigating the influence of CAP on specially designed mesoporous silica-coated superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (MSPIONs) for potential combination therapy in targeting skin cancer cell lines.

Amorphous and mesoporous silica coated SPION-clusters with varying pore sizes were synthesized by microwave-assisted solvothermal route. Synthesized particles were exposed to A375 and A431 cell lines, which in turn were exposed to CAP.

SEM, TEM results showed relatively mono-dispersed spherical SPION clusters, with pore size ranging from 4 to 11 nm. CAP was applied for various durations. There was a significant decrease in viability in both cell lines starting from the 5th second when CAP was applied, while there was no significant change in viability upon CAP exposure in the presence of MSPIONs.

These results confirm the biocompatibility of the modified with SPION clusters little cytotoxicity at very high concentrations. No synergistic effects have been observed in combination of clusters with CAP. In the future research focus, we will load anti-cancer drugs into particles and assess interactions with CAP

Acknowledgements: CAP applications on cells made by accessing the facilities at University Medical Center Rostock via an STSM within the PlasTHER. The project received funding from The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (222S690-2519 TUBITAK-COST) and Istanbul University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit (TDK-2022-39501).

P9. EXPLORING SILVER NANOSTARS AS ANTIBACTERIAL AGENTS AGAINST STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS

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Keywords: *Silver nanostars, Metal nanoparticles, Antibacterial, Antibiofilm, Nanomedicine.*

ABSTRACT.

The alarming rise of multidrug-resistant bacteria has prompted the development of novel and effective antimicrobial solutions¹. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are promising candidates, due to their low eukaryotic cytotoxicity and broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, with several antibacterial mechanisms of action described². From the AgNPs reported, silver nanostars (AgNSs) have shown enhanced antimicrobial potential but have their biomedical application largely unexplored³.

AgNSs were synthesized by a simple two-step method at room temperature⁴. Their morphology was assessed by UV-Vis spectroscopy and transmission electron microscopy, whereas dynamic light scattering and zeta potential determined their size and charge. The antibacterial and antibiofilm activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* are being determined by estimating the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) using the standard microdilution assay, and the minimum biofilm inhibitory concentration (MBIC) with crystal violet staining to quantify biofilm formation.

We will present our results on the synthesis, biophysical characterization, and evaluation of the antibacterial properties of AgNSs against *S. aureus*. The biophysical characterization revealed the size distribution (\bar{x} = 141±16 nm), surface charge (zeta potential = -44±3 mV), and star-shaped morphology of the synthesized AgNSs. MIC and MBIC data for *S. aureus* will also be presented.

This study successfully synthesized AgNSs and explores their potential as antimicrobial agent against *S. aureus*. Furthermore, understanding the mechanisms of action of AgNSs against bacteria will be crucial for establishing their biomedical application.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by "la Caixa" Foundation in the scope of the CaixaImpulse Health Innovation 2023 project (CI23-10134) and Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia – Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Ensino Superior (FCT-MCTES, Portugal) project 2022.01991.PTDC.

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P10. PREDICTION OF ENDOCRINE DISRUPTIVE ACTIONS OF UV-B FILTER OCTYLMETHOXYCINNAMATE ON TRANSTHYRETIN PROTEIN: INSIGHTS FROM *IN SILICO* AND *IN VIVO* STUDIES

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Keywords: *thyroid hormone transport, molecular docking, Danio rerio, gene expression, thyroid disruption.*

ABSTRACT

Ultraviolet (UV) filters are endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), and the impact of their exposure is a current concern for human health. The thyroid-axis is one of the main targets of EDCs action. Despite recent advances on identifying EDCs able to impair the thyroid-axis, the relationship between mechanism-based macromolecular interactions and human adverse outcomes remains to be understood. Development of *in silico* (molecular docking) and *in vivo* (assays with zebrafish developing embryos) methodologies is an excellent strategy to disclose these disruptive thyroid interactions. According to hazard identification, altered hormone transport across cell membranes is EDC's key characteristic No. 7. Our study focused on transthyretin (ttr), one of the most important thyroid hormone transport proteins, which is critical for normal fetal development. This work aimed to predict the binding of the octylmethoxycinnamate (OMC) a UV filter widely used in the cosmetic industry, to the ttr protein, thereby inferring its potential thyroid-disrupting action.

Molecular docking simulations were performed to verify the binding of OMC to the ttr protein. The expression of *ttr* gene was evaluated in zebrafish developing embryos exposed during 120h to OMC (0.004 - 4 mg/L).

Our results reveal a favorable binding of OMC on ttr consistent with an increased mRNA expression level of the protein.

Exposure to the OMC might disrupt thyroid action. Our findings highlight the need to reduce UV filters' exposure to maintain the thyroid homeostasis.

Acknowledgements: Authors acknowledge FCT funding by Ph.D. fellowship (2020.06616.BD, M.L.) and national funds (article 23, of the Decree-Law 57/2016, of August 29, changed by Law 57/2017, of July 19, DOI: 10.54499/DL57/2016/CP1482/CT0160, C.Q.; UIDB/00709/2020+UIDP/00709/2020, CICS-UBI; and UIDP/50017/2020+UIDB/50017/2020+LA/P/0094/2020, CESAM).

P11. USING MOLECULAR DOCKING TO FIND INHIBITORS FOR SARS-COV-2 NON-STRUCTURAL PROTEINS 14 AND 15

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Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, Molecular Docking, Antivirals, Drug Design*

ABSTRACT

Since the outbreak of SARS-CoV-2 in late December 2019 [1], researchers have been trying to target its proteins in an attempt to inhibit key functions. Non-structural proteins 14 (nsp14) and 15 (nsp15) are responsible for maintaining correct RNA proofreading [2], being crucial for the viral replication process, rendering them promising targets.

A Molecular Docking screening was performed on a list of Drugbank-approved ligands. Some of the best were experimentally tested to determine if they would inhibit nsp14 and nsp15. These most promising inhibitors were further analyzed by a second Molecular Docking pipeline, this one with more in-depth calculations, to better understand the protein-ligand interactions.

One of the compounds presented the lowest free energy of binding mode obtained using AutoDock 4 [3] against nsp14's ExoN active site with a value of -20.13 kcal/mol. Interestingly, AutoDock 4 also predicted a promising binding pose of this best compound with nsp15's NendoU active site with a free binding energy of -11.68 kcal/mol.

These results open possibilities for future designing of similar compounds to improve their binding affinity to nsp14 and/or nsp15. This suggests new ideas and alternatives to treat COVID-19.

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P12. STUDYING CYTOCHROME C OXIDASE PROTON PUMPING MECHANISM WITH CONSTANT-pH MD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Quantum Mechanics, Bioenergetics, Computational Biophysics*

ABSTRACT

Cytochrome c Oxidase (CcO) is the terminal enzyme of the electron transport chain, catalyzing the reduction of molecular oxygen to water while pumping protons against their concentration gradient^[1]. Despite the comprehensive knowledge about the individual parts of CcO, the contribution of the electronic transport and the gating phenomena to the pumping mechanism is still not completely understood. Proton pumping has been suggested to be dependent on the loading and unloading of protons at the Proton Loading Site (PLS), which in turn is coupled with electron transfer, linking conformation shifts and redox reactions^[2]. In this work, we used computational methods to create a model of CcO with increased realism to study the molecular details of the proton pumping mechanism.

The stochastic titration constant-pH molecular dynamics^[3] method allows the sampling of protonation events throughout an MD simulation. This allows studying the impact of oxidation state changes in the electrostatic profile of our protein, as well as the identification of key proton-exchanging residues.

We will be presenting preliminary results regarding cofactor parameterization and system setup. These are key steps of this work, considering the important role of these metal complexes in the protein's architecture and function, and the fact that CcO is a membrane protein.

Ensuring the proper parameterization and equilibration of both the protein and the embedding membrane is fundamental to setting up the foundation to apply more complex methods with confidence.

Acknowledgements: Foundation for Science and Technology Portugal (2023.01155.BD, CEECIND/02300/2017, UIDB/04046/2020, and UIDP/04046/2020)

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P13. FINE-TUNING MEMBRANE PERMEABILITY: UNRAVELING THE ROLE OF PH, HYDROGEN BONDS, AND HALOGEN BONDS IN COBIMETINIB TRANSPORT

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Keywords: Halogen Bonds, Lewis Base, Permeability, Anti-Tumor Drugs, CpHMD

ABSTRACT

Membrane permeability is a pivotal aspect in several biological processes, directly shaping the ADMET properties, and thereby playing a crucial role in rational drug design. The permeation of small molecules is intricately governed by various factors, including the pH [1] and the presence of chemical groups that are prone to establish specific noncovalent interactions. While hydrogen bonding (HB) is well-studied in this context, the less explored halogen bond (XB) also holds significance due to its potential role in membrane permeability, mediated by halogen-membrane recognition phenomena [2]. In this work, we investigate the permeation mechanism of Cobimetinib, an anti-cancer drug, at relevant pH conditions, addressing both the physiological pH (7.5) and the tumor acidic microenvironment (pH=6.0).

We used QM calculations to generate the RESP charges considering the anisotropic features of the halogen through the implementation of an extra-point (EP) model. Subsequently, we conducted US-CpHMD simulations in a POPC membrane model to compute the permeability coefficients for both Cobimetinib systems by employing the ISDM approach.

We observed that the formation of XBs, through the implementation of the EP (more realistic), led to more reduced permeability values when compared with the control system. Additionally, this drug exhibited increased permeability at both pH conditions, suggesting that Cobimetinib's high hydrophobicity might surpass the effect of the acidity, reported for other Lewis bases.

Overall, the findings from this study offer valuable insights into designing pH-specific anti-tumor drugs, while also emphasizing the significance of accounting for noncovalent interactions in the process of membrane permeation.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge FCT for projects UIDB/04046/2020 and UIDP/04046/2020 (BiolSI) and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 (M.M) and CEECIND/00381/2021 (P.J.C).

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P14. MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDIES TO INVESTIGATE CYSTEINE RESIDUES IN HYDROGEN SULFIDE SYNTHESIZING ENZYMES

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Keywords: Cystathionine γ -lyase; Hydrogen sulfide; Cysteine; Molecular Dynamics Simulations

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is a signaling molecule that regulates many processes in human physiology. Human enzymes that endogenously synthesize H₂S are cystathionine β -synthase (CBS), cystathionine γ -lyase (CSE), 3-mercaptopyruvate sulfurtransferase (MST) and Selenium-binding protein 1 (SELENBP1), which are related to the etiology of various cancers[1]. While most studies report increased expression of these enzymes in the cancer context, less is known about how they are regulated at the post-translational level[1]. These enzymes have a high number of non-disulfide cysteine residues. Their side chain thiol groups can undergo a variety of oxidative post-translational modifications (oxPTMs), being key regulators of redox homeostasis and signaling in proteins. Studying these oxPTMs can provide insights into these pathways and processes and how they relate to diseases associated with oxidative stress[1]. CSE cysteine-to-serine variants have been experimentally used to probe the role of individual Cys residues and their oxPTMs[2].

Methodology: Variants with cysteine residues substituted by serine were generated in PyMol to evaluate the impact of these substitutions on the protein structure and dynamics and provide insights regarding their physiological roles. Molecular dynamics simulations of 1 μ s are being carried out by GROMACS 2021.7 of these variants and the wildtype enzymes.

Results: The impact of these substitutions on the structure and function of the enzyme can be appreciated from the obtained results, namely regarding conformational flexibility evaluated by root-mean-square deviation and fluctuation, secondary structure, and principal component analysis.

Conclusion: MD simulations enable unraveling the impact of this type of cysteine substitutions, particularly in correlation with reported experimental data.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the PhD Fellowship 2022.13172.BD and iNOVA4Health (UIDB/04462/2020 and UIDP/04462/2020).

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P15. HAVE YOU HAD YOUR COFFEE TODAY? THE IMPACT OF CAFFEINE ON THE INTERACTIVE PROFILE BETWEEN SELECTED COMMERCIAL DRUGS AND PLASMATIC ALBUMIN

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Keywords: *Albumin-Drug Interactions, Drug-Displacement, Spectroscopy, STD-NMR, Molecular Docking.*

ABSTRACT

About 80% of the Portuguese population consumes products that contain caffeine (CAF) mainly due to the social-cultural aspects (27%), boost energy (22.9%), and deal with stress (22.7%). Before and during COVID-19, coffee average intake was 2.40 ± 0.84 and 2.68 ± 0.88 cups/day, respectively, confirming that CAF consumption is a normal habit in Portugal [1]. Human serum albumin (HSA) is the main globular protein responsible for the biodistribution of both endogenous and exogenous compounds, including clinically prescribed drugs [2,3]. In this sense, the interaction albumin/drug is crucial for the pharmacokinetic profile of drugs, thus, the present work reports the CAF effect on the binding capacity of HSA for some clinically relevant drugs, e.g., anti-inflammatory (ibuprofen, ketoprofen, and ketorolac), anticoagulant (warfarin), and anti-heart arrhythmia (digitoxin) by biophysical techniques, including UV-Vis, steady-state fluorescence, time-resolved fluorescence, saturation transfer difference nuclear magnetic resonance (STD-NMR), isothermal titration calorimetry, and molecular docking calculations. CAF and the isolated drugs might interact spontaneously with albumin via a moderate ground-state association. It was detected by multiple techniques that the binding of ibuprofen, ketoprofen, ketorolac, and digitoxin to HSA is not perturbed in the presence of CAF, however, the binding affinity HSA:Warfarin was drastically affected by CAF. Overall, these results indicated that there is not any positive or negative cooperativity of CAF for drugs that interact with subdomains IIIA (site II) and IB (site III), however, drugs that bind into subdomain IIA (site I) might be negatively influenced by CAF concentration in the human bloodstream, disrupting the residence time and pharmacokinetic profile of these drugs.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) through the projects from CQC: UIDB/00313/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/00313/2020>) and UIDP/00313/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/00313/2020>). O.A.C. also thanks FCT for his PhD fellowship 2020.07504.BD.

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P16. MODELING H₂O₂ RELEASE AND TRANSPORT IN THE EXTRACELLULAR MEDIUM IN TISSUES

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Keywords: *hydrogen peroxide concentrations, redox signaling, reaction-diffusion modeling.*

ABSTRACT

H₂O₂ regulates numerous physiological processes, but its concentrations and action range in the extracellular medium remains uncertain. These depend on an interplay between cellular release rates, membrane permeability, and how much it depletes intracellular antioxidant pools.

We modeled H₂O₂ release to the extracellular medium and its diffusion in tissues where it can permeate into the cells and be cleared by peroxiredoxins, glutathione peroxidases and catalase. We modeled the dynamics of these enzyme systems in each cell by a system of ordinary differential equations, and the diffusion of extracellular H₂O₂ from 11.6 or 58 μm radius spherical release regions through a diffusion equation in spherical coordinates. We considered a 10 μm/s permeability constant, typical for human tumor cell lines, and area-specific H₂O₂ production rates ν 0.2 - 200 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹, the highest representing an extreme situation corresponding to the production by activated macrophages.

The highest extracellular H₂O₂ concentrations attained at steady state at the center of the largest producing region ([H₂O₂]_{max}) at the highest considered ν was 19 μM. There was <20% depletion of the peroxiredoxin pool under these conditions. [H₂O₂]_{max} decreased just slightly for the 11.6 μm radius region. Thus, for production regions on the scale of a cell diameter local absorption is the dominant clearance process, rather than diffusion away from the region. [H₂O₂]_{max} is approximately proportional to the specific production rate over the considered ν range.

Altogether, the results suggest that [H₂O₂]_{max} in excess of a few μM, capable of extensively oxidizing the main intracellular antioxidant pools, are very unlikely to occur under physiological conditions.

Acknowledgements: Work financed by the European Regional Development Fund, through COMPETE2020-Operational Program for Competitiveness and Internationalization, and Portuguese funds via FCT-Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, under projects UIDB/04539/2020, UIDP/04539/2020, LA/P/0058/2020, UIDB/00313/2020, UIDP/00313/2020, UIDB/04564/2020 and UIDP/04564/2020 and under the Verão com Ciência 2020 program (Portugal). M.G. thanks the support of national funds from FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. through grant SFRH/BD/136046/2018.

P17. A CERAMIDE-BASED *STRATUM CORNEUM* SUBSTITUTE: TOWARDS A NOVEL *IN VITRO* PERMEATION SCREENING TOOL

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Keywords: *Biomimetic models, skin permeation, biophysical studies*

ABSTRACT

Skin topical administration and percutaneous permeation are appealing bioactive delivery routes, but they present challenges that must be carefully addressed during formulation development. As a result, an increasing number of researchers are working to create cutting-edge, economically viable, and successful *in vitro* percutaneous permeation models for the early stages of pharmaceutical, drug formulation, and cosmeceutical development.

The barrier provided by the Stratum Corneum (SC) intercellular lipid matrix, which is primarily composed of ceramides (CERs), cholesterol (Chol), and free fatty acids (FFA), poses the most difficult challenge for topically administered bioactives. These components are intricately organized in the intercellular lipid matrix in two crystalline coexisting lamellar phases with typical repeating distances of 13 and 6 nm (long periodicity phase (LPP) and short periodicity phase (SPP)). The current study's main goal was to create an innovative, well-standardized SC substitute (SCS) with an intercellular lipid matrix model for percutaneous permeation studies. In this regard, a CER-based lipid model was created and biophysically characterized in various lipid assemblies, including monolayers, bilayers, and liposomes. Surface-pressure isotherms, UV-Vis reflection spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry, Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR), Brewster Angle Microscopy, and Atomic Force Microscopy were used to test the CERs-based lipid mixture's ability to mimic the SC complex organization. The SCS was then embedded in various membrane scaffolds, characterized using ATR-FTIR and X-ray diffraction, and visualized with confocal, atomic force, scanning electron, and Raman microscopy. Finally, SCS was used as an *in vitro* percutaneous tool to assess percutaneous permeation of two bioactive compounds (diclofenac and caffeine). The results were compared to published data and showed promising results, implying that the SCS could be used in both pharmaceutical and cosmeceutical development in a controlled and reproducible manner.

P18. EVALUATION OF BILE ACID BINDING CAPACITY OF *LACTARIUS DELICIOSUS* WILD MUSHROOMS POLYSACCHARIDES AND ITS EXTRACTS

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Keywords: *Mushroom, Polysaccharide, Bile Salts Sequestration, Cholesterol Homeostasis*

ABSTRACT

The consumption of mushrooms is associated with bioactive benefits, namely enhancement of cardiovascular health [1]. Several studies have demonstrated the hypocholesterolemic effects of mushroom powders and also their extracts rich in polysaccharides [2]. However, the structure-function relationship between mushroom polysaccharides and the cholesterol-lowering effects is not well understood.

Polysaccharides extraction of *Lactarius deliciosus* originated from two Portuguese regions (Bragança and Mangualde) were obtained through aqueous extraction and further fractionated with ethanol precipitation using 50% (Et50) and 80% (Et80). The glycosidic linkage analysis of Et50 was determined by GC-MS of the partially methylated alditol acetates. The bile salts binding capacity of the aqueous extract and Et50 were tested using *in vitro* intestinal simplified model and measured by ¹H NMR.

The aqueous extract (SnH₂O) and fraction Et50 are rich in polysaccharides, mainly glucose, galactose and rhamnose. The glycosidic linkages analysis of Et50 showed the presence of glycogen-like structures and a rhamnosylated galactan. Results showed that the fraction Et50 (Mangualde) had a highest bile salts sequestration capacity (15%), followed by the raw extracts from Bragança mushrooms had 7% (SnH₂O) and 2% (Et50).

Aqueous extract and fraction Et50 of *Lactarius deliciosus*, both rich in polysaccharides, showed to sequester bile salts. This capacity can be influenced by polymerization and ramification degree of polysaccharides. This work represents a contribution of strengthening the comprehension of structure-function relationship of mushroom polysaccharides and their impact on cholesterol homeostasis.

Acknowledgements: Project Safe2Taste (MTS/BRB/0056/2020 DOI 10.54499/MTS/BRB/0056/2020). Helena Laronha thanks FCT/MCTES and ESF through NORTE 2020 (Programa Operacional Região Norte) for her PhD grant (Ref. 2022.13262.BD). Elisabete Coelho thanks Portuguese national funds (OE), through FCT, I.P., in the scope of the framework contract foreseen in the numbers 4, 5 and 6 of the article 23, of the Decree-Law 57/2016, of August 29, changed by Law 57/2017, of July 19 (CDL-CTTRI-88-ARH/2018 - REF. 049-88-ARH/2018). Filipe Coreta-Gomes acknowledge the research contract funding due to LAQV-REQUIMTE (UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020) project.

Funding: Supported by Safe2Taste (MTS/BRB/0056/2020 DOI 10.54499/MTS/BRB/0056/2020), FightSterol (PTDC/QUI-OUT/29373/2017) funded by FCT/MCTES through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and Compete 2020. The authors also acknowledge the funding through LAQV/REQUIMTE (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020).

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P19. AQUAPORIN-3 AND ROTTLERIN: NATURAL COMPOUNDS AS PROMISING TARGETS TO TACKLE CANCER

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Keywords: Aquaporins, Cancer, Inhibitors.

ABSTRACT

Aquaporins (AQPs) are specialized transmembrane protein channels that facilitate the passive transport of water, glycerol and other small solutes across cell membranes, in response to osmotic or solute gradients. These channels are involved in many physiological functions, maintaining homeostasis in different organs and tissues [1]. However, aquaporins such as AQP1 and AQP3, have been identified as aberrantly expressed in different types of cancer [2,3]. Thus, these proteins have emerged as promising pharmacological targets prompting the discovery of AQP inhibitors for cancer therapy. Since most inhibitors reported so far have high toxicity lacking selectivity, we decided to develop an innovative structure-based in silico computational workflow to find AQP inhibitors, where a polyphenol was identified. Rottlerin was tested for its inhibitory effect on AQP1 (water channel) and AQP3 (water and glycerol channel) by measuring water and glycerol permeability in human red blood cells that endogenously expressing these AQPs, using stopped-flow spectroscopy. Rottlerin showed to strongly inhibit AQP3 glycerol permeability ($IC_{50} = 6.7 \pm 2.97 \mu M$). To validate the results obtained, yeast cells overexpressing human AQPs were used. Rottlerin showed no effect on yeast-hAQP1 activity but induced pronounced yeast-hAQP3 inhibition (73%), corroborating the results obtained previously [4]. Rottlerin seems to establish a robust and consistent interaction with several residues at the extracellular surface region of AQP3, acting as a stereochemical cap that blocks glycerol from accessing the pores of the protein [4]. Thus, our data shows that Rottlerin strongly inhibits AQP3 activity revealing its potential as a new drug for cancer therapy.

Acknowledgements: FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, grant PTDC/BTM-SAL/28977/2017, fellowship 2020.04974.BD to C. Pimpão, fellowship 2023.01323.BD to I. Paccetti-Alves and projects UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa.

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P20. FROM CODE TO STRUCTURE: MOLECULAR MODELING IN BIOMATERIALS ASSEMBLY

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Keywords: *Peptide Assembly, Protein Aggregation, Biomaterials, Molecular Modeling.*

ABSTRACT

Molecular modeling and simulations of biomolecules has been growing in the last decades thanks to software optimization and rapid hardware improvements. Atomistic and coarse-grained molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of proteins have become more accessible, user-friendly, and implemented in many protein research projects.

The usage of current atomistic and coarse-grained force fields and MD software can be employed in the study of peptide and protein self-assemble and structural stability. Here, examples of computational studies of monomeric and assembled peptides and proteins are presented: i) the conformation changes of a designed tripeptide in monomeric and assembled states; ii) a structural model of the assembly of a reflectin-based peptide [1]; iii) a phosphotyrosine-binding oligopeptide conformational analysis computational alanine scanning [2]; iv) coarse-grained simulation of reflectins' aggregation in different protonation states.

The presented examples demonstrate multiple unique capabilities of molecular modeling techniques applied to the study of biomaterials. Through atomistic and coarse-grained MD it is possible to enrich research strategies in biomaterials by predicting geometric and physico-chemical properties, crucial for understanding the mechanisms and material characteristics obtained from wet-lab experiments. Please answer the following sections.

Acknowledgements: Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 899732 (PURE), national funds from FCT I.P., UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 UCIBIO, the project LA/P/0140/2020 i4HB, PTDC/CTM-CTM/3389/2021, 2022.15912.CPCA.A1, 2023.10436.CPCA.A1, support by INCD funded by FCT & FEDER 01/SAICT/2016 n^o 02215, C.E. 2022.0788.GEECIND/CP1725/CT0002, SFRH/BD/147388/2019 for I.L., 2022.11305.BD for C.S.

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P21. AQUAPORIN-3 INHIBITION BY ORGANOGOLD COMPOUNDS IMPAIRS MELANOMA CELL ADHESION, PROLIFERATION AND MIGRATION

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Keywords: *Aquaporin-3, melanoma, organogold compounds, permeability*

ABSTRACT

Aquaporin-3 (AQP3) is a transmembrane channel that facilitates the transport of water, glycerol and H₂O₂ across cell membranes. AQP3 is reported to be aberrantly expressed in melanoma and is implicated in cell adhesion, migration and proliferation. Gold compounds can inhibit AQP3 activity with reduced associated toxicity, being considered promising compounds for cancer therapy.

In this study, we screened the inhibitory effect of a new series of gold compounds derived from Auphen, a potent AQP3 inhibitor, on AQP3 permeability in red blood cells (RBCs) that highly express AQP3, through stopped-flow light scattering. The effect of these compounds was validated in AQP3-overexpressing HEK-293T cells and their physiological influence was ascertained in two human melanoma cell lines. In parallel, we confirmed the results in AQP3-silenced melanoma cells.

Two organogold compounds were found to be promising AQP3 inhibitors on the RBCs assays while some gold derivatives showed moderate reduction of glycerol permeation and drastic decrease of H₂O₂ permeability in the AQP3-overexpressing HEK-293T cells and the melanoma cell lines. Moreover, all organogold compounds were tested for their impact on cellular processes and the results showed an impairment in cell adhesion, proliferation and migration in a cell type-dependent manner.

Our results demonstrate that AQP3 peroxiporin activity is crucial for melanoma progression and unveils gold compounds as promising AQP3 blockers with impact on melanoma cell adhesion, proliferation and migration, suggesting their potential as anticancer molecules against AQP3-overexpressing tumors.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, Portugal, through grants PTDC/BTM-SAL/28977/2017 and 2022.06601.PTDC, researcher contract 2022.03691.CEECIND to I.V.d.S., fellowship 2020.04974.BD to C.P., strategic projects UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa, and TUM Global Postdoctoral Fellowship to S.R.T.

P22. PERMEATION OF WEAK ACIDS AND BASES THROUGH VESICLES FORMED FROM CELL MEMBRANES

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Keywords: *cell membranes, fluorescent pH probe, drug permeation*

ABSTRACT

Drugs and other xenobiotics are usually not recognized by transporters, and the optimization of their passive permeation is a crucial step in drug development. The pH-variation assay allows following the permeation of weak acids and bases, where the faster permeation of the neutral species and consequent equilibration with its ionized forms leads to changes in the pH inside the lipid vesicles, and has shown a reasonable correlation with *in-vivo* absorption[1,2]. Better correlations are anticipated with biomembranes from relevant physiological barriers. However, live cell-based assays introduce variability and complexity, complicating the establishment of relations between permeability coefficients and drug structural properties.

In this work, we prepared and characterized membrane vesicles from Caco-2 cells, considered good *in-vitro* models for intestinal epithelium. The vesicles containing the fluorescent pH probe HPTS were used to obtain the permeability of several drugs. A ratiometric detection method was used to improve robustness in the quantification of the pH variation.

The vesicles obtained from Caco-2 cells were relatively homogeneous with an average diameter close to 300 or 500nm, and a polydispersity index of 0.5. Large pH variations were observed upon addition of several drugs, with the pH increasing/decreasing when bases/acids were added, as expected. Although qualitatively the results were similar to those obtained with liposomes, important qualitative and quantitative differences were observed, highlighting the relevance of using native membranes to evaluate passive permeation through the relevant physiological barriers.

The methodology developed allows the use of native cell membranes to evaluate passive permeation using the pH-variation assay. Comparison with the results for simple lipid vesicles and native membranes from other cells lines will provide a better understanding of passive permeation through distinct physiological barriers, being a promising methodology for drug design and development.

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P23. MIR-155-3P DETECTION BY MOLECULAR BEACON BEAD-BASED ASSAY

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Keywords: *Molecular Beacon, Microfluidics, Lung Cancer, MicroRNAs, Fluorescence.*

ABSTRACT

Lung cancer (LC) is one of the most common deadly cancers worldwide. Therefore, it is imperative to identify novel therapeutic targets and treatments. In the diagnostic field, microRNAs (miRNAs) have emerged as potential biomarkers to follow several diseases including LC and its progression. However, the detection and quantification of miRNAs is time-consuming and expensive when using traditional approaches such as PCR. Herein, we explore detecting miR-155-3p that is overexpressed in LC using a molecular beacon (MB) bead-based assay immobilized in a microfluidic device. This method is based on the increase of fluorescence emitted by the MB when the target binds it by Watson and Crick complementarity. This bound will change the MB conformation from a stem-loop to a linear conformation that leads apart the fluorophores on each extremity. Its combination with a microfluidic device allows an easy and fast detection of the target. Herein, we detected it in saline solution with a limit of detection (LOD) of 48 nM. Then we tested the method on more complex biological samples, A549 cells' total RNA and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs), spiked with the target miRNA, obtaining a satisfactory recovery, especially in A549 cells' total RNA. This work brings one more step in the development of easy, cheap, and fast tools to detect and quantify potential biomarkers for LC.

Acknowledgments: This work was developed within the scope of the CICS-UBI projects UIDB/00709/2020 and UIDP/00709/2020, UIDP/04378/2020, and LA/P/0140/2020, financed by national funds through the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology/MCTES. Thanks are due to FCT for doctoral grants 2023.02001.BD, 2021.04785.BD, and 2021.07695.BD “Bolsa de Investigação em Oncologia Dr. Rocha Alves do Núcleo Regional do Centro da Liga Portuguesa Contra o Cancro”, Instruct-ERIC Pilot R&D application ID 2473, and PAPILOMA ref. CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-181235.

P24. INHIBITION OF AQUAPORIN-9 WATER AND GLYCEROL PERMEABILITY BY GOLD COMPOUNDS SHED LIGHT ON INFLAMMATION THERAPEUTICS

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Keywords: *Aquaporin, organogold compounds, water and glycerol permeability, selectivity, inflammation*

ABSTRACT

Aquaporin-9 (AQP9) is a membrane channel with dual aquaglyceroporin/porixoporin activity, facilitating the diffusion of water, small non-charged solutes such as glycerol, and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) through cell membranes. AQP9 altered expression is found in inflammatory conditions, such as sepsis. Gold(III) compounds selectively and potently inhibit AQP3, with reduced associated toxicity, making them promising molecules for the therapy of AQP3-associated diseases. In this study, we aimed to identify potential functional inhibitors of AQP9 with inflammation reduction application, using a series of organogold compounds (**1**, **2** and **3**) derived from Auphen, a potent aquaglyceroporin inhibitor.

To ascertain the compounds' selectivity, HEK-293T cells were transfected to overexpress AQP9. After transfection validation (qPCR and immunoblotting), the harmless concentration of compounds to perform functional assays was determined by MTT colorimetric assay. Then, the effect of gold compounds on water/glycerol permeability was evaluated in AQP9-overexpressing cells using stopped-flow light-scatter spectroscopy.

Cell viability assays revealed gold compounds to be harmless or inducing residual cell cytotoxicity. For water permeability assessment, light scattering signals were analyzed using an exponential fit revealing an impairment in water permeability in cells incubated with compound **3** and Auphen. For glycerol permeability assessment, signals were fitted with a linear regression revealing an inhibition of glycerol permeability by all four compounds, where **1** was the most potent, followed by **2**, Auphen and **3**.

These findings highlight the potential of targeting AQP9 for therapeutic intervention in pathologies where AQP9 is implicated, such as inflammatory and hepatic diseases.

Acknowledgements: To FCT for funding: project 2022.06601.PTDC, UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa, research contract to IVS (2022.03691.CEECIND), 2020.04974.BD to CP, and 2023.01323.BD to IPA, and to ERASMUS+ Programme for funding the practical trainings to OPG.

P25. BRIDGING THE GAP: NUCLEAR BIOMECHANICS IN THE AGEING PUZZLE

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Keywords: *Ageing, nuclear envelope, lipids, lamin A, nuclear biomechanics*

ABSTRACT

Ageing involves cellular and molecular alterations, leading to physiological decline. Among the identified ageing hallmarks is altered mechanical properties. Here, we explore the correlation between nuclear envelope (NE) biomechanical integrity loss and ageing. Several studies have underscored the role of the structural protein lamin A (LA) in the ageing process. However, the impact of nuclear lipids on NE dynamics and nuclear structure is unclear. Thus, our work aims to study how variations in NE biophysical properties influence LA binding to the membrane as age progresses, contributing to nuclear biomechanics regulation.

Nuclei from skin fibroblasts of healthy young and elderly donors, and progeria patients, were isolated using a novel protocol employing fluorescence-activated nuclei sorting. Confocal microscopy, atomic force microscopy (AFM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were used to characterize the quality of isolated nuclei, their morphology and lamin distribution.

Upon optimization, our new isolation method resulted in fully isolated nuclei from primary cells with minimal contamination with other cell organelles. Moreover, as observed through TEM, the NE seems to be intact, without loss of major nuclear content. The biophysical properties of the NE membrane in these isolated nuclei are currently being explored using fluorescence lifetime imaging (membrane tension), generalized polarization (membrane order) and AFM-based force spectroscopy (elasticity), to evaluate age-associated variations. As for LA distribution, similarities are also expected between healthy old volunteers and progeria patients samples.

This research explores the role of nuclear lipid-protein interactions in NE dynamics during healthy ageing and disease, advancing our understanding of age-related cellular changes.

P26. OPTIMIZING TAXIFOLIN DELIVERY TO CERVICAL CANCER CELLS THROUGH ALBUMIN-BASED NANOCARRIERS

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Keywords: *Albumin, Taxifolin, Targeted delivery, Cervical cancer.*

ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer remains a significant global health concern, with over 340,000 lives lost annually. To address this challenge, novel therapeutic approaches are being explored, with natural compounds showing promise. These compounds exhibit a unique ability to selectively target malignant cells while sparing healthy tissues, marking a notable advancement in cancer treatment strategies. Taxifolin, a natural compound renowned for its anti-cancer properties, has shown potential in inhibiting the cervical cancer oncoprotein E6. However, its efficacy is hindered by limited bioavailability, necessitating the development of advanced delivery systems for optimal therapeutic impact.

The utilization of albumin and DOPE liposome-based delivery systems has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance the effectiveness of taxifolin administration. These carriers capitalize on the synergy between them to precisely target overexpressed albumin receptors on cervical cancer cells. Characterization studies revealed that the systems possess sizes of 101.23 ± 1.05 nm, a surface charge of -22.5 ± 3.24 mV, and an encapsulation efficiency of $79.26 \pm 3.61\%$. Furthermore, viability assays conducted on HPV-positive cancer cells (HeLa) demonstrated an IC_{50} of 68.27 μ M, while exhibiting no toxicity towards healthy cells (human fibroblasts).

These findings shed light on a promising pathway for the development of precision therapies in cervical cancer treatment. They underscore the significance of targeted drug delivery strategies in improving therapeutic outcomes, offering hope for more effective and less toxic treatments in the fight against cervical cancer.

Acknowledgements: This work was developed within the scope of the CIGS-UBI projects UIDB/00709/2020 and UIDP/00709/2020, financed by national funds through the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology/MCTES. Miguel Ferreira also acknowledges the doctoral fellowship from FCT ref: 2023.01957.BD. Diana Costa acknowledges FCT her Assistant Researcher Contract 2021.03946.CEECIND.

P27. PH-RESPONSIVE NANOPARTICLES FOR THE PROTECTION AND DELIVERY OF RNA TO CANCER CELLS

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Keywords: *Nanoparticles, pH-responsive polymers, POEOMA-b-PDPA, small RNAs, RNA delivery.*

ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles are gaining increasing attention due to their relevance for delivering biopharmaceuticals for gene-based therapies. In parallel, RNA is being explored to establish innovative therapies. However, this success is highly dependent on the effective delivery of these biomolecules to target cells. The development of pH-responsive nanoparticles may improve the delivery efficiency in certain diseases presenting a microenvironment with deregulated pH, like cancer.

In this work, it is explored the pH responsiveness and efficiency of a copolymer composed of poly(2-(diisopropylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (PDPA) and poly(oligo(ethylene oxide)methyl ether methacrylate) (POEOMA) for encapsulation and release of small RNAs (sRNA). The encapsulation process is based on the electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged sRNA and the protonated tertiary amine groups of the PDPA segment[1]. Three copolymers with different architectures (linear or 4-arm star-shaped) and compositions (4-arm star PDPA-*b*-POEOMA or 4-arm star POEOMA-*b*-PDPA) were synthesized by atom transfer radical polymerization. The sRNA encapsulation and release efficiencies of the copolymers were studied by UV spectroscopy and agarose electrophoresis. The best formulations were further characterized regarding the size and surface charge of the polyplexes, by DLS and ELS, respectively.

Depending on the copolymer, concentration, and pH of the formulation, the systems reached complexation efficiencies between 35% and 84%. The polyplexes presenting higher encapsulation efficiencies had sizes ranging from 92 to 104 nm. Given the pH-responsive nature of the copolymers, it was possible to achieve a release efficiency of 75% by increasing the pH to 7.4.

This research demonstrates the potential of pH-sensitive polymers as promising RNA delivery systems.

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P28. ANTIBODY-LIGAND INTERACTIONS ON A HIGH-CAPACITY STAPHYLOCOCCAL PROTEIN A RESIN: INSIGHTS FROM SEM AND SAXS ANALYSES

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Keywords: *Antibody-Ligand Interactions, Staphylococcal Protein A affinity chromatography, Scanning electron microscopy, Small-angle X-ray scattering.*

ABSTRACT

The process of purifying antibodies via Staphylococcal Protein A affinity chromatography serves as a critical stage in platform production procedures, facilitating the manufacturing of biopharmaceuticals. Throughout the years, there have been notable advancements in refining the structure of ligands, augmenting ligand density, and optimizing methods for immobilization, as well as enhancing bead properties and backbone composition. These efforts have been directed towards improving dynamic binding capacity (DBC) and operational efficiency. Notably, enhancements in DBC have been achieved by consolidating repetitive antibody binding domains into singular ligand structures and increasing the quantity of binding domains. Despite these advancements, there remains a significant gap in comprehending the interaction during chromatographic processes.

This study places significant emphasis on employing advanced techniques to elucidate the binding orientation of the antibody-staphylococcal protein A complex. Through a comprehensive analysis utilizing adsorption isotherms, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), the spatial distribution, orientation, and stoichiometry of protein A to the resin TOYOPEARL® AF-rProtein A HC have been clarified. In-situ monitoring of chromatographic steps using SAXS further reveals the interaction between antibodies and the resin, with findings supported by adsorption isotherms. These techniques provide intricate insights into monolayer adsorption, stoichiometry, and reversible protein-protein interactions, shedding light on the spatial distribution of Protein A ligands and enhancing the understanding of antibody purification through protein A affinity chromatography.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG – grant number 824186 and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology/MCTES – CICS-UBI projects UIDB/00709/2020 and UIDP/00709/2020.

P29. MUCIN \mathcal{O} -GLYCAN RECOGNITION BY SALMONELLA SII E ADHESIN FOR TARGETED ANTI-ADHESION THERAPY

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Keywords: *SiiE Giant Adhesin, Salmonella, Bacterial infection, Host-Glycans*

ABSTRACT.

Mucin \mathcal{O} -glycan domains play a vital role in the gastrointestinal tract, serving as recognition sites for adhesins of both commensal and pathogenic bacteria. While they typically form a protective barrier against pathogens, some pathogenic strains, such as Salmonella, exploit mucin \mathcal{O} -glycans for adherence and invasion. Salmonella infection poses a significant public health concern, compounded by the emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains and the associated economic burden. Understanding the mechanisms underlying host-glycome/pathogen-lectin recognition is crucial for developing effective anti-adhesion strategies. The non-fibrillar Salmonella SiiE giant adhesin has been identified as a key player in engaging Mucin-1 (MUC1) through sialic acid-containing \mathcal{O} -glycans. Consequently, targeting the SiiE-MUC1 interaction holds promise for infection prevention, offering an alternative approach to combat bacterial resistance.

To elucidate the specificity and molecular determinants governing mucin \mathcal{O} -glycan recognition by SiiE, we employ a comprehensive methodology combining microarrays, mucin cell-based arrays, and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). This approach allows for high-throughput screening as well as detailed insights into molecular structure and dynamics, essential for understanding SiiE's molecular recognition.

Our study initiates with optimizing the recombinant expression and purification of SiiE, succeeded by functional testing and high-throughput screening.

Through an integrative and innovative methodology, our goal is to enhance comprehension of lectin-adhesins from bacteria. Ultimately, this research aims to facilitate the development of potent anti-adhesion molecules for combating Salmonella infections.

Acknowledgements: The authors thank FCT-Portugal for the projects 2023.00074.RESTART, EXPL/QUI-OUT/0069/2021, 2022.06104.PTDC. GLYCOTwinning project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417 funded by European Commission. H. C. and F.M also thank the CEEC contracts (2020.03261.CEECIND and CEECINST/00042/2021 (UCIBIO-NOVA-FCT), respectively). The National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013-PINFRA/22161/2016, co-financed by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORK and FCT through PIDDAC).

P30. A WELL-INFORMED *IN SILICO* APPROACH TO ACHIEVE SIGNIFICANT IMPROVEMENTS IN THE CHALLENGING BATTLE AGAINST LUNG CANCER

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Keywords: *FIH1, pocket similarity, machine learning, Drug Design, Lung Cancer*

ABSTRACT

Lung cancer remains a major cause of mortality worldwide, killing approximately 1.8 million people a year, and the five-year survival rate is a dismal 15%. Lung cancer is frequently detected only at an advanced stage. The typical survival period for patients with synchronous multiple primary lung cancer (MPLC) is around 31 months, particularly for those who are not candidates for surgery. Remarkably, 50.8–57.9% of MPLCs display comparable histological features [1]. It is well established that elevated HIF-1 α levels encourage carcinogenesis in lung cancer. On the other hand, HIF-1 α can be downregulated by focusing on HIF1AN, a regulatory factor for the protein. HIF1AN therefore becomes a potentially attractive therapeutic target lung cancer treatment [2].

Because HIF1AN is a new target with only a few known “active” compounds, we employed various *in silico* techniques to explore active site similarities with well-characterized proteins. This approach aims to find targets that share molecular binding sites (pockets) with an existing target that is devoid of active molecules. Through utilizing established ligands from these “comparable targets”, we were able to identify potential novel FIH1 ligands. This strategy assumes that structurally distinct targets can exhibit significant binding pocket similarities, influencing their interactions with small molecules [3].

Our analysis of pocket similarities between all FIH1 structures available in the Protein Data Bank, and their pocket similarities range from very low (0.24) to perfect (1), despite all structures belonging to the same protein. This highlights the potential for identifying matching pockets in other proteins with known ligands to screen for potential ligands for FIH1.

This work demonstrates that even within the same proteins, variations in pocket similarity can occur. However, recognizing these fluctuations can be crucial for setting the appropriate threshold when searching for related, well-studied proteins with known ligands for potential therapeutic targets.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, Portugal, through a PhD fellowship awarded 2022.13497.BD, COMPETE LISBOA-01-0246-FEDER-000017, UIDB/04138/2020, and UIDP/04138/2020.

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P31. GALLIC ACID-TRIETHYLENE GLYCOL APTADENDRIMERS: SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

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Keywords: *Gallic acid-triethylene glycol dendrimers; G-quadruplex aptamers; aptadendrimer; biophysical studies*

ABSTRACT

Cancer is a major public health problem that, unfortunately, is growing up worldwide. Chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and surgery are the preferred therapies; however, off-target activity/reactivity and toxicity are major shortcomings. One of the best ways to address these weaknesses is using drug delivery systems that enhance the tumor targeting, uptake, and internalization of the drug by the tumor cells. Several nanostructures, such as dendrimers, have been used to deliver drugs [1]. Dendrimers are synthetic tree-like macromolecules composed of repetitive layers of branching units that are prepared in a controlled iterative process, through generations with discrete properties [2]. Aptamers have been widely used as promising targeting moieties due to hallmark properties, such as low immunogenicity, easy synthesis, and high specific binding affinity [3]. They can be used to modify drug-loaded nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery.

Herein, we described the synthesis of an aptadendrimer by covalent bioconjugation of a gallic acid-triethylene glycol (GATG) dendrimer with the G-quadruplex (G4) AT11 aptamer (a modified version of AS1411) at the surface. We evaluated the loading and interaction of an acridine orange ligand, termed C8, that acts as an anticancer drug and binder/stabilizer of the G4 structure of AT11. Both steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence anisotropy evidenced the interaction between the aptadendrimer and C8.

Release experiments show a delivery of C8 after 4 h. Also, the cell viability, uptake and delivery were evaluated into prostate cancer and healthy cell lines. Aptadendrimers tend to localize in the cytoplasm of various cell lines studied as demonstrated by confocal microscopy. The internalization of the aptadendrimers is not nucleolin-mediated or by passive diffusion, but via endocytosis. MTT studies with prostate cancer cells and non-malignant cells evidenced high cytotoxicity mainly due to the C8 ligand. The rapid internalization of the aptadendrimers and their fluorescence properties make them attractive for the development of potential nanocarriers.

Acknowledgements: André Miranda acknowledges the research fellowship from “Rede Nacional de Ressonância Magnética Nuclear” (ref. PINFRA/22161/2016-B4) and the doctoral fellowship Grant from FCT—Foundation for Science and Technology (ref. 2021.04785.BD). J. Lopes-Nunes acknowledges the doctoral fellowship grant from the FCT—Foundation for Science and Technology ref. 2020.05329.BD. A.M.M. acknowledges the Junior Researcher position under the FCT CEECindividual call (CEECIND/00884/2017). The authors thank Alexander Fedorov for assistance with time-resolved fluorescence measurements. C.C. acknowledges the grant from FCT ref. UIDP/00709/2020, project PAPILOMA ref. CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-181235, “Bolsa de Investigação em Oncologia Dr. Rocha Alves do Núcleo Regional do Centro da Liga Portuguesa Contra o Cancro” and project INOV+ Ecossistema de Inovação Inteligente, funded by CENTRO 2020, through Fundo Europeu de Desenvolvimento Regional ref. CENTRO-01-0246-FEDER-000044.

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P32. INSIGHTS INTO THE DYNAMIC SELF-ASSEMBLY OF CEPHALOPODS SPECIFIC PROTEINS

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Keywords: *cephalopods, structural proteins, reflectin, self-assembly, protein assembly*

ABSTRACT

A fascinating source for developing bio-based and sustainable materials involves reflectins, the structural proteins found in cephalopods. *In vivo*, reflectins function as static and dynamic biological Bragg-reflectors responsible for cephalopods' camouflage¹. Optical properties are triggered by phosphorylation/dephosphorylation events that promote protein assembly/disassembly into high-order structures². We studied *in vitro* the stimuli-induced reversible self-assembly of reflectins. For that, two protein sequences were selected with different amino acid sequences, derived from static iridocytes (light organ reflectors), and from dynamic iridocytes (cephalopods' skin). Both proteins were recombinantly produced and purified. They were further characterized by circular dichroism (CD), dynamic light scattering (DLS) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) to assess reversible self-assembly into nanoparticles in function of pH. Our experimental data was supported by molecular simulations at different pH conditions using coarse grained reflectin models. According to our results, the amino acid composition of each reflectin greatly impacts their final biophysical properties and reversible self-assembly to external stimuli. Our study contributes to understand the self-assembly mechanism of reflectin proteins, with impact in the design and engineering of bio-based advanced functional materials.

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (Portugal) for projects PTDC/BII-BIO/28878/2017, PTDC/CTM-CTM/3389/2021, and Research Unit on Applied Molecular Biosciences – UCIBIO (UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020) and Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy – i4HB (LA/P/0140/2020). The authors thank FCT/MEC for the research fellowship SFRH/BD/147388/2019 for I.L and 2022.11305.BD for C.S.

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P33. NANODIAMONDS FOR RNA EXTRACTION FROM BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES

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Keywords: *RNA capture, Nanodiamonds, Purification, Design of experiments, Solid-phase extraction.*

ABSTRACT

The research in the RNA-based therapeutics field has shown promise for various applications. However, large-scale RNA production remains challenging and costly. Recovery and purification are high-burden steps, being time-consuming and an economic challenge. This study seeks to enhance RNA capture and recovery, aiming for greater efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Carbon-based nanomaterials, particularly nanodiamonds (NDs), offer a promising solution, due to their large surface area, tuneable surface properties, and high biocompatibility.

Different NDs were screened to assess their effectiveness in adsorbing and recovering RNA while promoting different interactions. An experimental design was employed to fully characterize the adsorption and recovery. Also, adsorption isotherms were determined. A thorough analysis of the impurities was performed when a sample from an *E. coli* lysate was used. RNA secondary structure was assessed using circular dichroism.

All materials demonstrated a high ability to adsorb RNA; nevertheless, RNA recovery was only feasible with oxidised NDs (NDs-ox). Furthermore, the maximum adsorption capacity of the ND-ox obtained from the Langmuir equation was 86.908 mg/g. The selective adsorption of RNA over DNA was confirmed, revealing no visible contamination via agarose gel electrophoresis. Moreover, a significant reduction of 91.7% in total protein content was observed between the initial and recovered samples from the lysate. Finally, the circular dichroism analysis confirmed the RNA integrity.

Overall, the findings highlight the potential of NDs-ox in effectively capturing RNA, streamlining the pre-purification process, and showcasing promising prospects for applications in RNA-related studies for biomedical purposes.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge the projects UIDB/00709/2020, UIDP/00709/2020, UIDB/50020/2020, UIDP/50020/2020, UIDB/50006/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 and LA/P/0045/2020 (ALiCE) financed by national funds through FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC). PF acknowledges FCT for the PhD fellowship (2022.13803.BD). SACC acknowledges the Scientific Employment Stimulus - Institutional Call (CEECINST/00102/2018).

P34. ON THE MAPPING OF DRUGGABLE POCKETS ON THE ED DOMAIN OF INFLUENZA NS1 PROTEIN – A REVIEW

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Keywords: *Influenza; Druggable Pockets; NS1; Target Protein, PI3K, TRIM25*

ABSTRACT

Flu is a highly contagious disease caused by the Influenza virus (Orthomyxoviridae family) affecting around 10% of the world's population every year [1]. Anti-Influenza vaccines are widely used as a prophylactic measure. However, even if updated annually, vaccines have limited effectiveness since new viral strains are constantly emerging. Hence, more efficient therapies must be developed. The influenza virus expresses various groups of proteins, such as polymerases, matrix proteins, and non-structural proteins [1].

Influenza virus non-structural protein 1 (NS1) is a highly conserved protein exclusively expressed in virus-infected cells [1-2]. NS1 mediates essential functions in viral replication and pathogenesis, through a multitude of molecular interaction partners, host cell activities, and structural plasticity [1–3]. Among various mechanisms, NS1 interacts with the cell host proteins PI3K and TRIM25 leading to viral replication and apoptosis inhibition [3,4]. Therefore, NS1 is a promising anti-influenza target, given its conserved structure.

NS1 is composed of two structural domains, RNA-binding domain (NS1-RBD) and the effector domain (NS1-ED) [1,4]. Several druggable pockets on the surface of NS1-ED domain have already been identified by our research group [2,4]. Some druggable pockets co-localize with stable binding regions of protein–protein interaction sites of NS1-PI3K and NS1-TRIM25, suggesting that these pockets are promising new targets for antiviral development [3]. Molecules with higher resilience to viral resistance may lead to a new class of antiviral drugs with activity against a broad spectrum of infections caused by the influenza virus. Here, structural aspects regarding the druggability of NS1 will be revised and discussed.

Acknowledgements: Authors thank the financial support of Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) via PhD scholarship UI/BD/154536/2022 to C. Peralta and UIDB/00313/2020 & UIDP/00313/2020 funds to CQC-IMS.

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P35. DESIGN OF NOVEL MOLECULES WITH POTENTIAL ANTIPSYCHOTIC ACTIVITY INTEGRATING AN *IN SILICO* APPROACH

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Keywords: *Schizophrenia, Antipsychotics, Serotonin 2A receptor, Molecular docking.*

ABSTRACT

Inspiration from a classic antipsychotic led to a molecule whose mixture of its two isomers showed high antagonist activity at the serotonin 2A receptor (5-HT_{2A}R). This receptor is associated with schizophrenia and depression, and several drugs used to treat these and other diseases have an antagonist activity at the 5-HT_{2A}R^{1,2}. Initial biological tests suggested that only one of the isomers may be responsible for the high activity. An *in silico* approach was developed to identify the isomer and to provide additional detail into the binding determinants for this promising receptor.

The approach involved the application of protein-ligand docking using 6 independent scoring functions (SF), the structures of the 5-HT_{2A}R complexed with different ligands, and a detailed optimization of the docking conditions through re-docking. The optimized protocol was used to predict the binding conformation of the isomers and their relative binding affinity. A computational procedure was applied to optimize the affinity of a selection of molecules to the target and other pharmacological properties.

One of the isomers showed stronger binding affinity towards 5-HT_{2A}R with all SF and consistency in the poses. A surprising observation on ligand-receptor interaction opened new possibilities of applications for our molecule. New structures were designed *in silico* leading to novel promising compounds.

The integrated use of these *in silico* methodologies represents an economical, fast strategy for drug design and development, essential for the initial stages of the process as an attempt to optimize time and resources, and to increase the probability of success from bench to clinic.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499 /UIDP/50006/2020), FCT/MCTES (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020 and UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020), through national funds.

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P36. INTERACTION OF MRI CONTRAST AGENT [Gd(DOTA)]⁻ WITH LIPID MEMBRANES: A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY

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Keywords: *Contrast Agents for MRI, Molecular Dynamics Simulation, Lipid bilayers, Partition, Water proton relaxivity.*

ABSTRACT

Contrast agents are important imaging probes in clinical MRI, allowing the identification of anatomic changes that otherwise would not be possible. Intensive research on the development of new contrast agents is being made to image specific pathological markers or sense local biochemical changes. The most widely used MRI contrast agents are based on Gadolinium(III) complexes that includes [Gd(DOTA)]⁻ (DOTAREM®), a standard reference where several chemical modifications have been introduced to improve key properties. Due to their very high charge density, they have low permeability through tight biological barriers such as the blood-brain barrier, hampering their application in the diagnosis of neurological disorders. In this study, we explore the interaction between [Gd(DOTA)]⁻ and POPC lipid bilayers by means of molecular dynamics simulations. The parametrization protocol of Gd-based complexes was previously published in our lab.¹ The simulations unveil detailed insights into the agent's interaction with the lipid bilayer, offering perspectives beyond experimental methods. Various properties, including the impact on global and local bilayer properties, were analyzed. As expected, the results indicate a low partition coefficient (K_p) and high permeation barrier for this reference compound. Nevertheless, favorable interactions are established with the membrane leading to moderately long residence times and influencing the physical-chemical attributes of [Gd(DOTA)]⁻ as a MRI contrast agent. This work establishes a reference framework for the use of simulations to guide the rational design of new contrast agents with improved relaxivity and bioavailability, and for the development of liposome-based formulations for use as imaging probes or theranostic agents.

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P37. FLUORESCENT PROBES *CIS*- AND *TRANS*-PARINARIC ACIDS IN FLUID AND GEL LIPID BILAYERS: A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY

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Keywords: *fluorescence spectroscopy, lipid membranes, membrane probe, molecular dynamics simulations*

ABSTRACT

Fluorescence probes are indispensable tools in biochemical and biophysical membrane studies. Most of them possess extrinsic fluorophores, which often constitute a source of uncertainty and potential perturbation to the host system. In this regard, the few available intrinsically fluorescent membrane probes acquire increased importance. Among them, *cis*- and *trans*-parinaric acids (*c*-PnA and *t*-PnA, respectively) stand out as probes of membrane order and dynamics. These two compounds are long-chained fatty acids, differing solely in the configurations of two double bonds of their conjugated tetraene fluorophore. In this work, we employed all-atom and coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulations to study the behavior of *c*-PnA and *t*-PnA in lipid bilayers of 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) and 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), representative of the liquid disordered and solid ordered lipid phases, respectively. All-atom simulations indicate that the two probes show similar location and orientation in the simulated systems, with the carboxylate facing the water/lipid interface and the tail spanning the membrane leaflet. The two probes establish interactions with the solvent and lipids to a similar degree in POPC. However, the almost linear *t*-PnA molecules have tighter lipid packing around them, especially in DPPC, where they also interact more with the lipid choline groups. Probably for these reasons, while both probes show similar partition (assessed from computed free energy profiles across bilayers) to POPC, *t*-PnA clearly partitions more extensively than *c*-PnA to the gel phase. *t*-PnA also displays more hindered fluorophore rotation, especially in DPPC. Our results agree very well with experimental fluorescence data from the literature and allow deeper understanding of the behavior of these two reporters of membrane organization.¹

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P38. AQUAPORINS AND IMMUNITY: NEW TARGETS FOR INFLAMMATORY DISEASES THERAPY

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Keywords: *Aquaporin, Inflammation, Immunity.*

ABSTRACT

The ability of immune cells to shift shape for migration, phagocytosis or antigen uptake is supported by crucial proteins, such as aquaporins (AQPs), that regulate volume changes. AQP3 and AQP9 are water, glycerol, and hydrogen peroxide channels. Although highly expressed in macrophages and neutrophils, AQPs role in inflammation is still unclear. Here, we activated the NLRP3 inflammasome in macrophages to investigate AQPs role in inflammation.

AQP3 contribution to cell volume changes was assessed by measuring water and glycerol permeability. Moreover, we took advantage of the selective AQP3 inhibitor Auphen to study the role of AQP3, the most expressed AQP in THP-1 monocytic cells, in the production of IL-6 and activation of inflammasome. AQP3 was silenced as a complementary approach. To study the influence of AQP3 in membrane changes during priming cells were stimulated with LPS, while for inflammasome activation cells were stimulated with nigericin, ATP or glycerol hyperosmotic challenge.

AQP3 inhibition/silencing partially blocked LPS-priming and decreased production of IL-6, suggesting an involvement of AQP3 in macrophage priming via NF- κ B. Moreover, AQP3-dependent cell reswelling increased IL-1 β release through caspase-1 activation. Inflammasome activation was also blocked when AQP3 was inhibited/silenced.

AQP3 involvement in priming and inflammasome activation points towards AQPs as potential players in the setting of the inflammatory response. These findings prompted us to develop an antibody against the most representative AQP in human primary immune cells, anti-AQP9, to reduce inflammation and with potential applications in clinics and impact in other diseases where AQP9 has a pathophysiological role.

Acknowledgements: To FCT for funding: project 2022.06601.PTDC, and strategic projects UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa, and Stimulus of Scientific Employment Program to IVS (2022.03691.CEECIND).

P39. ESTABLISHMENT OF AN *IN VITRO* MODEL OF INFLAMMATION TO STUDY THE REGULATION OF AQP3 BY miRNAs

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Keywords: *Aquaporins, miRNAs, inflammation.*

ABSTRACT

AQP3, a water, glycerol and H₂O₂ channel, is the most representative AQP in macrophages with a preponderant role in cell priming and inflammasome activation. Discovering AQP3-specific inhibitors would prompt the reduction of inflammation. Since AQP3 inhibitors may present off-target effects, the high targeting specificity and lack of cytotoxicity of miRNAs offer an advantageous alternative. In this project, we aim to develop an in vitro model to study AQP3 modulation by miRNAs. Compelling evidence suggests that Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF α) and all-trans retinoic acid (atRA) impair AQP3 expression in human trophoblasts and human keratinocyte cells, respectively. Here, we hypothesize that modulation of AQP3 by TNF α and atRA is an indirect effect of miR-AQP3 interaction.

THP1 monocytic cells were used as a model of inflammation. Macrophage-like cells were induced by PMA. Cells were treated with TNF α or atRA and modulation of AQP3 expression was evaluated by qPCR and peroxiporin activity using fluorescence microscopy. Putative AQP3-interfering miRNAs were identified using miRNet platform.

Our results showed an impairment of AQP3 expression in TNF α - but not for atRA-treated cells. An impaired influx of H₂O₂ was registered with both TNF α and atRA treatments, corroborating the AQP3 expression levels with TNF α but not with atRA, possibly due to transcriptional and translational regulation. Moreover, using bioinformatic tools we identified miRNAs as putative AQP3 inhibitors, miR-124 and miR-874-3p, two crucial modulators of inflammation and innate immunity.

These data will allow building a model to study AQP3 modulation by miRNAs with implications for immunity and the inflammatory response.

Acknowledgments: To FCT for funding: project 2022.06601.PTDC, UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa, and research contract to IVS (2022.03691.CEECIND).

P40. FLAVONOIDS AND OMEGA-3 FATTY ACID-LOADED LIPID NANOCARRIERS AS PROMISING ANTIMICROBIAL BIOFILM STRATEGIES

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Keywords: *Biofilms, resveratrol, quercetin, omega 3 fatty acids, lipid nanocarriers.*

ABSTRACT

Biofilms are 3D microorganism clusters adhered to a biotic (host tissue) or abiotic (inert material) surface or interface and encased in a protective self-produced hydrated extracellular matrix of proteins, polysaccharides, and extracellular DNA. Biofilms on medical devices and body tissues cause many antibiotic treatment failures and chronic infections. Biofilm removal is hard, and new strategies are required to eliminate it. Nanocarriers (NC) can transport antibiofilm agents. NCs' small size, large surface, adhesion, and deformability can be tuned to enhance passage of antibiofilm agents through the biofilm barrier.

Lipid NC, containing flavonoids (quercetin and resveratrol) and omega-3 fatty acids, were produced by lipid film hydration and high-shear homogenization techniques, and characterized regarding size, surface charge and shelf stability. Biofilm susceptibility trials assessed NC's effect on *S. aureus* biofilms using colony-forming unit (CFU) counting. Biofilms formed by adding 1 mL of *S. aureus* (1×10^6 CFU mL⁻¹) to 24-well tissue culture plates with coverslips, incubating for 2 hours at 37°C and 100 rpm. After rinsing with 0.9% NaCl, fresh medium containing NC was added for further incubation (24 and 48 hours, 37°C, 100 rpm). Tryptic soy broth without NC served as a positive control. Sessile populations were detached via 1-minute sonication.

Lipid nanocarriers were homogeneous, with hydrodynamic size <200 nm, and negatively charged. They were stable for at least for 4 weeks and presented an encapsulation efficiency of flavonoids >70%. Preliminary results show that flavonoid-loaded lipid nanocarriers may be a promising strategy as anti-biofilm agent.

P41. COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF BIOPHARMACEUTICALS PURIFICATION SYSTEMS

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Keywords: *Affinity Chromatography, Affinity Ligands, Biopharmaceuticals, Virtual Screening.*

ABSTRACT

Affinity Chromatography is a cornerstone in purifying biopharmaceuticals for therapeutics and diagnostics, with the market projected to hit \$300 billion by 2025. Large-scale antibody production is costly, largely due to the use of expensive biological ligands like Protein A¹. To address this, our project focuses on discovering synthetic affinity ligands tailored to bind antibodies, utilizing the Petasis-Ugi scaffold with four R-groups for fine-tuning affinity². For instance, the B1A12A2 ligand, based on this scaffold, has shown affinity for IgG, Fab, and Nanobody structures³. Through the screening of virtual compound libraries, we can effectively minimize the number of compounds requiring experimental testing while optimizing chemical diversity. Employing the Petasis-Ugi scaffold alongside commercially available building blocks sourced from eight distinct chemical vendors, we have enumerated an expansive *in-silico* combinatorial library comprising approximately 66 million structures. The combinatorial library will undergo screening against a target antibody using molecular docking calculations, leveraging deep learning techniques, especially crucial given the vast number of compounds involved. Afterwards, to extract critical information on the protein-ligand interactions Molecular Dynamics simulations of the best hits will be performed. Integrating experimental design, virtual screening, and molecular dynamics simulations, this project is poised to expedite the discovery of new synthetic affinity ligands with robust binding affinity to antibodies, while striving to low the cost of biopharmaceutical production.

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 899732 (PURE Project), national funds from FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., in the scope of the project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 of the Research Unit on Applied Molecular Biosciences – UCIBIO, the project LA/P/0140/2020 of the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy – i4HB, the projects, PTDC/CTM-CTM/3389/2021, 2022.15912.CPCA.A1, 2023.10436.CPCA.A1, support by INCD funded by FCT and FEDER under the project 01/SAICT/2016 n^o 02215.

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P42. EXTENDING THE ST-CPHMD METHOD TO AMBER14SB TO SEARCH FOR NON-OPIOID ANALGESICS

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Keywords: *CpHMD, AMBER14SB, Stochastic Titration, Analgesics, Non-opioid.*

ABSTRACT

Acid-sensing ion channels (ASICs) are voltage-insensitive, proton-gated cation channels in membranes, widely expressed across the central and peripheral nervous systems, that are involved in physiological processes ranging from nociception to brain ischemia [1]. ASICs are activated by extracellular acidosis and ligands can act as antagonists or agonists for the channel's affinity for protons [2]. To discover ASIC activity modulators, one must understand the pH effects on the protein channel that result in altered cation membrane permeability.

Constant-pH Molecular Dynamics (CpHMD) methods are pivotal in describing pH and its effects on the conformational space of biological systems [3]. The stochastic titration CpHMD (st-CpHMD) method has shown excellent performance over the years [3,4].

Until recently, our implementation of the st-CpHMD method only supported the GROMOS 54A7 [3] and the CHARMM36m force fields [4]. We have now extended this method to also support AMBER 14SB, a force field particularly suited for studying disordered proteins and membrane channels, by proposing a small modification to the official ff14SB atomic partial charges to make them st-CpHMD-compatible.

We have made the st-CpHMD method and the AMBER 14SB force field fully compatible and are now ready to study ASICs activity at different pH values.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) for funding through projects UIDB/04046/2020 & UIDP/04046/2020 and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and 2022.10517.BD. 17.BD. This work was also funded by the European Union (TWIN2PIPSA, GA 101079147). We also acknowledge the HiPerGator supercomputer.

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P43. *IN SILICO* EVALUATION OF NOVEL STEAP1 ANTAGONISTS FOR PROSTATE CANCER

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Keywords: *Prostate Cancer, STEAP1, Structure-Based Drug Design, Therapeutic Inhibitors.*

ABSTRACT

Prostate cancer (PCa) is the second most frequent cancer diagnosed in males. The Six-Transmembrane Epithelial Antigen of the Prostate 1 (STEAP1) is a transmembrane protein highly overexpressed in PCa, functioning as a metalloreductase, particularly towards iron complexes, and contributes to excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), being linked to oxidative stress responses, which culminate in the activation of pro-oncogenic genes.

The Enamine “Discovery Diversity Set-10” was screened to identify potential antagonists. The coordinates of arginine’s and lysine’s which compose and surround the core heme binding site of STEAP1 were averaged to define a centroid and expanded 12 Å. Molecular docking was performed with GOLD’s genetic algorithm and ligands were selected based on the consensus of ChemPLP, ChemScore, GoldScore, ASP, Vina and Vinardo scoring functions. Most promising ligands were evaluated with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and free energy calculations.

Consensus scoring yielded 3 promising compounds (Z1171328906, Z1143443933 and Z1842122377). All compounds exhibited a similar docked pose, stacked with the heme group in the center of the binding site. Analysis of MD trajectories indicate a shift towards the helix 4-extracellular domain interface for the ligands, with varying degrees of “mobility”. MMPBSA/MMGBSA revealed moderate free energies of binding and energy decomposition analysis exposed shared key aminoacid interactions and was consistent with ligand migration.

The simulations provide critical insight into the binding site dynamics/interactions and tentative modes of binding and are valuable for the discovery of small drug molecules to inhibit the electron transfer mechanism and mitigate ROS generation.

P44. UNDERSTANDING A NEW RESPIRATORY ROUTE IN *GEOBACTER*: CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INNER MEMBRANE CBC3 COMPLEX

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Keywords: *Geobacter*, extracellular electron transfer, quinone-cytochrome *c* oxidoreductase complexes, multiheme cytochromes

ABSTRACT

Geobacter species are known for their unique metabolic capabilities, with special relevance to the usage of several extracellular compounds as terminal electron acceptors, such as insoluble metals, in extracellular electron transfer (EET) [1]. *Geobacter sulfurreducens* is the best studied *Geobacter* species and gene-knockout and proteomics studies were used to identify essential proteins for the EET mechanisms. One crucial step in this process is the transfer of the electrons from the quinone pool to the inner membrane associated quinone-cytochrome *c* oxidoreductase complexes for subsequent transfer to their redox partners in the periplasm. *G. sulfurreducens* genome encodes for six inner membrane oxidoreductase gene clusters, from which three of them, CbcL, ImcH and CbcBA, have already been implicated in specific metabolic pathways [2,3]. The target of this study is the complex Cbc3, which is composed of an anchored multiheme α -type cytochrome (CbcS), an iron-sulfur protein (CbcT) and an integral membrane subunit (CbcU).

The tetraheme periplasmatic domain of CbcS was heterologously expressed in *E. coli*, purified and characterized by various spectroscopic techniques to assess structural and functional features. UV-Visible potentiometric redox titrations were employed to measure the reduction potential of the protein, while Nuclear Magnetic Resonance was used to determine the spin state of the heme groups and to confirm the heme core arrangement predicted by an AlphaFold model. The results obtained bring new insights on the EET pathways of *Geobacter*.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through grants 2022.11900.BD (JMAA), PTDC/BIA-BQM/4967/2020 (CAS), EXPL/BIA-BQM/0770/2021 (LM), UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO), and LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB)

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P45. CUBOSOMES AS NANOCARRIERS OF ANTI-LEISHMANIA AGENTS

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Keywords: *Leishmania, nanodelivery systems, cubosomes.*

ABSTRACT

Leishmaniasis, a widespread tropical disease, impacts over 1 billion people annually, leading to 0.7 million new cases and 50,000 deaths. It is caused by a parasitic protozoa transmitted through infected sandfly bites, resulting in various forms of the disease. Visceral leishmaniasis (VL) caused by *Leishmania donovani* and *Leishmania infantum* is particularly severe, with a high fatality rate if left untreated. Current treatment options, primarily chemotherapy, suffer from limitations including toxicity, low efficacy, and emerging drug resistance. We have identified and tested a new class of anti-Leishmania agents, offering promise for a highly potent and non-toxic drug. However, these compounds exhibit low aqueous solubility, hindering *in vivo* testing. To address this issue and improve their pharmacokinetic profile, we propose loading the compounds into nanosystems that improve drug doses and increase their solubility: cubosomes. Cubosomes (Cubs) made of monoolein (GMO) and poloxamer-407 (P407) (1:8) were produced by emulsification and sonication methods. Cubs were characterized in terms of size, surface charge and colloidal stability by methods of Dynamic /Electrophoretic Light Scattering (DLS/ELS) Encapsulation of the anti-leishmania agent was performed by direct mixing and the corresponding encapsulation efficiency (EE) was determined by a validated quantification method. Loaded nanocarriers were characterized by the same techniques used for empty ones and those with the best physical-chemical properties (e.g., highest EE/LC and stability) will proceed to cellular *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. Cubosomes of 225 nm size, PDI 0.2 and negative surface charge (-25 mV) were obtained stable for at least 3 weeks. Passive targeting to macrophages will be assured by negatively charged surface. Maximum EE%=80.31% of anti-leishmania agent corresponded to 10x IC₅₀ amastigotes and an increase in drug solubility was also obtained.

P46. EXPLORING THE SITES OF INTERACTION OF NON-STEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS WITH ENZYMES IN THE LANDIS CYCLE

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Keywords: *Landis cycle, membrane, molecular dock, cell injury hepatocytic.*

ABSTRACT

Long-term use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs causes cellular alterations, mainly at the hepatic and renal levels. It is believed that these alterations are mainly due to membrane phospholipids, since these are precursors of inflammatory mediators after cell injury, thus serving as signalling agents for classes of enzymes such as cyclooxygenase and phospholipases A2. The main cycle that keeps membrane fluidity active is the Landis cycle. Therefore, this work sought to study the interaction of various known anti-inflammatory drugs, as well as various natural compounds with the main enzymes of the Landis cycle, these being lipoprotein-associated phospholipases A2, lysophosphatidyltransferase and cytosolic phospholipase A2. The aim of this study is to elucidate the molecular mechanisms that lead to the hepatic effects of long-term use of anti-inflammatory drugs.

In this work, a virtual screening of anti-inflammatory compounds was carried out using the GOLD molecular docking software to assess the binding ability and putative interactions between the chosen compounds and the main enzymes of the Landis cycle. To analyze the results, DataWarrior and Pymol were used.

A detailed comparison was made with data from the literature, demonstrating the main molecular interactions between the compounds and the proteins of the cycle, which cause alterations in the membrane and long-term damaging effects.

In our study, we demonstrated the possible interaction with enzymes in the Landis cycle of a variety of anti-inflammatory drugs associated to long-term enzymatic dysfunction, and that could cause diseases such as tumours, lipid dysfunction, and development of atherosclerosis.

Acknowledgements: LAQV/REQUIMTE "Associated Laboratory for Green Chemistry - Clean Technologies and Processes" DOI: 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020| 10.54499/UIBP/50006/2020| 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020| FCT BD.2023.00566

P47. PREDICTIVE MODEL FOR LASER-BASED PHOTOBIMODULATION DOSIMETRY PLANNING APPLIED TO OROFACIAL DISORDERS.

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Keywords: *low-level light therapy, Monte Carlo simulation, dosimetry, machine learning*

ABSTRACT

Laser-based Photobiomodulation (PBM) for treating orofacial diseases is a promising technology. However, detailed studies on the effect of skin phototype (SP) and body mass index (BMI) are scarce, but can be crucial to develop effective dosimetry planning tools. Therefore, a predictive model describing the effects of morphological and physiological parameters on laser dosimetry parameters would be a valuable tool.

A Monte Carlo (MC) light propagation model, involving a four-layer skin model representing different SPs and BMIs, and the settings of a typical oral PBM treatment protocol was developed. To overcome the computational burden associated with MC simulations, a machine learning predictive model (MLPM) based on multiple regression analysis was devised.

An extensive MC simulation study was conducted and used to train the MLPM. A set of 1144 MC simulations, across a representative group of tissue properties, was performed, using 660nm and 808 nm light, and a power of 100 mW. For the entire span of tissue properties, the muscle heat depositions were computed. The performance of the MLPM exhibited a good tradeoff between accuracy and computational cost.

The predictive model allows the selection of laser parameters, based on patient-specific morphological and physiological characteristics, to ensure therapeutic effectiveness at the target muscle tissue, while preventing unwanted temperature rise at superficial layers.

P48. SHEDDING SYNCHROTRON LIGHT TO EXPLORE THE SKIN-DEEP EFFECTS OF NANOPLATFORMS

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Keywords: *Hydrogels, nanoparticles, skin lipids, synchrotron-based FTIR microspectroscopy (SR-FTIR)*

ABSTRACT

Skin diseases are often characterized by lipid barrier disruption, which causes high transepidermal water loss, increased invasion by pathogens and consequent abnormal inflammatory response. In this project, hybrid hydrogels were designed to form a blend between marine polysaccharides and synthetic polymers, becoming a vehicle option to improve skin treatments. Since betamethasone is one of the mostly used corticosteroids to solve inflammation, but has several off-target side effects, this drug was incorporated into lipid nanoparticles to enhance its local effect on skin layers, upon their embedding in the hybrid hydrogel platform. The aim was to unravel the underlying mechanisms between nanoplatfoms and skin, regarding lipid chain conformation, lateral packing, and protein structures.

All nanoplatfoms were incubated for 8 h in porcine ear skin samples, cut in a cryo-microtome (5 μ m), and placed on CaF₂ slides. SR-FTIR measurements were performed at MIRAS beamline using the 3000 Hyperion microscope coupled to a Vertex 70 spectrometer, to obtain spectra in the frequency range 4000-900 cm^{-1} , in transmission mode. Microscope imaging allowed to determine the IR chemical maps of skin regions of *stratum corneum* and epidermis.

After treatment with the nanoplatfoms, skin spectra mainly in epidermis show lower wavenumbers shift for alkyl chain conformation peaks compared to untreated skin, which are characteristic of a more ordered skin barrier, with hexagonal lateral packing, and no evidence of protein denaturation.

Synchrotron-based FTIR microspectroscopy allowed to unveil a more ordered skin lipid structure induced by the nanoplatfoms, indicating their potential to re-establish skin barrier function.

Acknowledgements: This work received support and help from FCT/MCTES (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020 and UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020), through national funds. SCL thanks funding from CEECINST/00007/2021 (DOI: 10.54499/CEECIND/01620/2017/CP1427/CT0002). AIB thanks funding from FCT/MEC (SFRH/BD/147038/2019). These experiments were performed at BL01-MIRAS beamline at ALBA Synchrotron with the collaboration of ALBA staff.

P49. MEMBRANE PERMEABILITY OF HALOGENATED DRUGS: THE IMPACT OF HALOGEN ANISOTROPY

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Keywords: *Membrane permeability, halogenated drugs, halogen bonds, ADME properties, MD simulations*

ABSTRACT

Covalently bond halogen atoms possess anisotropic electrostatic potentials comprising both a positive (σ -hole) and negative region, and therefore, can establish interactions with electronegative species, called halogen bonds (XBs), and with electropositive molecules, for instance, being a hydrogen bond (HB) acceptor. Very recently, we showed that XBs mediate ligand-membrane interactions, thus indicating a potential role of XBs in the permeation of drugs, however, the full effect is still unknown.

Six commercially used halogenated drugs (diazepam, bromazepam, clonidine, metolazone, furosemide, and amiodarone) were studied by performing molecular dynamics simulations along with umbrella sampling. The halogen anisotropy was considered by the usage of an extra-point of charge (EP). The permeability coefficients (P_{calc}) were determined using the inhomogeneous solubility-diffusion model (ISDM) and a score based on the difference between the maximum and minimum of the calculated free energies ($\Delta G_{\text{ranking}}$).

Very high correlations ($R > 0.9$) between the calculated and experimental values were obtained using the ISDM model. The use of an EP allowed the sampling of XBs and did not interfere with the sampling of HBs.

The use of an EP does not have an impact on the P_{calc} , however, it allows the study of XBs without compromising the sampling of HBs.

Acknowledgements: FCT: SFRH/BD/146447/20119 (AFortuna), UIDB/04046/2020 (DOI: 10.54499/UIDB/04046/2020) and UIDP/04046/2020 (DOI: 10.54499/UIDP/04046/2020) to BioISI, 2021.00381.CEECIND (DOI: 10.54499/2021.00381.CEECIND/CP1650/CT0004) to PJCosta. EU: project TWIN2PISPA - Twinning for Excellence in Biophysics of Protein Interactions & Self-Assembly (GA 101079147).

P50. PARAINFLUENZA FUSION PEPTIDE AMINO ACID RESIDUES INVOLVED IN OLIGOMERIZATION AND MEMBRANE INTERACTION

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Keywords: *Parainfluenza, membrane fusion, fusion peptide*

ABSTRACT

Parainfluenza viruses cause a significant disease burden worldwide, especially in children. These enveloped viruses enter host cells by fusing their envelope with the cell membrane. The membrane fusion process is mediated by the fusion glycoprotein, which upon proteolytic cleavage exposes the fusion peptide (FP), able to insert into and destabilize the host membrane. Despite the crucial role of the FP in viral entry, the mechanism by which it promotes fusion is still not fully understood [1]. Previously, we demonstrated that the parainfluenza FP (PIFP) forms oligomeric water-permeable porelike structures in membranes, resulting in lipid disturbances, leakage, and fusion of vesicles. We also identified key amino acid residues in PIFP essential for peptide oligomerization and membrane interaction [2].

Here, we explore the function of these residues using a combination of biophysical experiments with membrane model systems and molecular dynamics simulations.

Our results reveal the importance of the PIFP N-terminus in membrane interaction and leakage induction in lipid vesicles. Furthermore, we found that the Q120 residue within the PIFP porelike structure, located in the membrane's hydrophobic core, facilitates crucial peptide-peptide interactions for pore formation.

Overall, our findings contribute to the understanding of PIFP-induced membrane fusion and offer insights for the development of viral entry inhibitors.

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P51. APPLICATION OF *IN SILICO* METHODS TO IDENTIFY PUTATIVE DRUGABLE CAVITIES ON THE MACHADO-JOSEPH DISEASE CAUSING PROTEIN

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Keywords: *Machado-Joseph disease, targeted protein degradation, molecular dynamics simulations.*

ABSTRACT

Machado-Joseph disease (MJD) is a rare, genetically determined disorder due to expansion of a polyglutamine track in the ATXN3 protein. Mutant ATXN3 aggregates in neuronal cells, causing their demise, with no effective treatment currently available. Target removal of mutant ATXN3 is a potential therapeutic approach, with small molecule-based therapies capable of inducing targeted protein degradation showing promise [1].

Currently, experimental structures for both normal and mutated forms of ATXN3 are unavailable. This study employs a combination of molecular modeling, including partial experimental structures and AlphaFold, along with extensive atomistic molecular dynamics, to generate high-accuracy fully atomistic 3D models for wild-type and mutant ATXN3, representing their dominant conformations.

The two resulting models were analyzed using various pocket/cavity hunting programs (Gecom, Castp, Cofactor, DeepSite, Pocasa, FTSite, DoGSiteScorer). A promising cavity was identified in the mutated ATXN3, encompassing amino acid residues from the expanded PolyQ track, characteristic of the mutant form. This suggests a potentially selective strategy for targeting only the mutated form.

A promising selective druggable cavity was identified in the mutated form. This cavity is currently being explored using structure-based virtual screening methods to select candidates for synthesis and subsequent biological evaluation.

Acknowledgements: This work received support from FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020), FCT/MCTES (LA/P/0008/2020 DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0008/2020, UIDP/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50006/2020 and UIDB/50006/2020 DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50006/2020), through national funds.

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P52. TOWARDS A COMPUTATIONAL METHOD FOR THE PREDICTION OF CORE INTERACTING RESIDUES

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Keywords: *Protein-protein interaction, Zernike polynomials, Shape complementarity, Electrostatic complementarity, Neural Networks.*

ABSTRACT

Predicting protein-protein interactions (PPIs) is crucial, given that over 80% of proteins function within molecular complexes that are central to biological processes. Cells are crowded with molecules and other components, among which proteins must recognize and adapt to bind, making complex formation highly specific. Proteins' binding regions display a combination of geometrical and chemical complementarities, which ultimately reflect on the binding stability.

Computational methods offer insight into single-molecule behaviors, aiding experimental studies. In this context, we proposed an algorithm based on the evaluation of shape complementarity at the interfaces using the Zernike 2D polynomial expansion, which can identify the interacting regions in ~60% of the analyzed cases [1]. The rotational invariance of these polynomials allows a quick blind-search for interacting patches.

Expanding the protocol to assess electrostatic complementarity discriminates between transient and permanent PPIs with a ROC AUC of 0.8 [2]. Preliminary tests employing a neural network integrating geometric and chemical descriptors, and the aforementioned features, achieved an accuracy of ~0.8 in identifying interacting residues.

This method could be employed to reinforce docking or pose selection algorithms, as well as to favor the development of new predictive tools for binding affinity.

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P53. UNLOCKING THE FUTURE OF DRUG DISCOVERY: FORWARD-THINKING APPROACHES TO PROTEIN BINDING SITE EXPLORATION

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Keywords: *Binding site; Pocket Detection; computational methods*

ABSTRACT

Research in drug discovery often concentrates on a limited portion (approximately 15%) of the human proteome, primarily focusing on well-studied genes and avoiding less explored areas. This practice overlooks a vast number of potential drug targets, with an estimated 85% of disease-associated targets remaining underutilized¹. Our research aims to bridge this gap by employing computational studies to detect and analyze protein binding sites, thereby identifying novel drug targets.

Our project categorizes proteins into three groups based on data from Oprea and colleagues, UniProt, ChEMBL, and the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The first group, Well-Known Targets (WKT), includes proteins with approved drugs or those in clinical trials. The second, Difficult to Obtain Pharmacological Effect (DOPE), consists of proteins that are challenging to model. The third group, Yet Not a Druggable Target (YNOTs), encompasses proteins without identified active compounds. We used CAVIAR software for pocket detection in each protein's PDB structure to identify binding sites². We then compared the cavities of DOPE targets with the binding sites of WKTs using Pocket Match software³.

Initial findings show that the allosteric center of Excitatory Amino Acid Transporter 1 (EAAT1) (PDB: 5ML3) has a high similarity score with the Phosphodiesterase 6 Delta Subunit (PDE6 δ) (PDB: 5LM4), positioning it as a prime candidate for further investigation. Similarly, when comparing the YNOTs group with the WKTs, cluster analysis identified 178 targets with similarity scores above 75%, and 4 targets with scores exceeding 80%.

These results suggest the potential for validating new drug targets and suggest the creation of a new database comprising structures that have remained unexplored but could serve as potential targets for small molecule therapeutics.

Acknowledgements: We thank the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) for financial support EXPL/QUI-OUT/1288/2021, 2022.03752.PTDC, CPCA/A2/6972/2020, UIDB/04138/2020, and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed.Ulisboa.

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P54. UNVEILING MSCs OSTEODIFFERENTIATION PATTERNS ACROSS DONORS THROUGH NON-INVASIVE NMR METABOLOMICS

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Keywords: *Stem cells, Osteogenic differentiation, Metabolic switch, Exometabolome, NMR metabolomics.*

ABSTRACT

The secretion profile of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) is a major driver of their therapeutic effects, e.g. in bone regeneration. However, some secretome constituents, namely metabolites, are still largely unexplored. In this context, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) exometabolomics may reveal new information on MSCs osteodifferentiation and clarify how the secretome reflects intracellular behavior, providing means to monitor differentiation.

Untargeted NMR metabolomics was applied to monitor exometabolome changes of human adipose-derived MSCs (hAMSCs) from 3 different donors throughout 21 days of osteodifferentiation, compared to proliferation alone (controls).

For all donors, both osteogenesis and proliferation involved i) consumption of glucose, glutamine, pyruvate, serine, and branched-chain amino acids (BCAAs), and ii) secretion of several energy-related compounds (e.g. Krebs cycle intermediates, creatine, phosphocreatine and lactate), BCAAs breakdown products, ornithine and histidine. During osteodifferentiation, cells underwent evident changes in metabolic activity, increasing serine and cysteine uptake, while reducing the excretion of histidine (mediates mineralization), creatine and phosphocreatine. Ornithine was highly secreted, most likely to avoid polyamines accumulation and subsequent osteodifferentiation inhibition. Simultaneously, there was less consumption of glutamine, BCAAs and glucose, suggesting glycolytic downregulation with redirection of pyruvate towards reduction to lactate. Exometabolome results were articulated with endometabolome changes in the same cells, providing further insight into the above-mentioned energy metabolic switch, as well as cell membrane metabolism, antioxidative protection and creatine biosynthesis.

The donor-independent features unveiled in this work may be exploited to monitor cell osteogenic ability and advance potential metabolic candidates for media optimization towards osteocommitment enhancement.

Acknowledgements: BetterBone (2022.04286.PTDC) & BIOIMPLANT (PTDC/BTM-ORG/28835/2017), through COMPETE2020/FEDER (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-028835); CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, UIDB/50011/2020 (DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50011/2020), UIDP/50011/2020 (DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50011/2020) & LA/P/0006/2020 (DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0006/2020), through FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC); SFRH/BD/150655/2020 (DSB PhD grant); National NMR Network (Project N^o022161) through FEDER (COMPETE 2020/POCI/PORL/FCT (PIDDAC)).

P55. A COMPUTATIONAL PIPELINE TO AUTOMATE GENE DISCOVERY AND ENZYME ENGINEERING

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Keywords: *Gene Discovery, Enzyme Engineering, Metabolic Pathways, Automated Platform.*

ABSTRACT

Poor expression, low catalytic levels, low concentrations of co-factors or substrates, toxicity towards the final product and other factors all contribute to the low performance of microorganisms using natural or novel pathways. Protein engineering is an effective strategy for improving metabolic pathways and overcoming these problems by re-designing an enzyme's catalytic properties in favor of a certain reaction (Du et al., 2011).

To address this problem, we developed an automated platform for gene discovery and enzyme engineering, which aims to find and enhance the enzymes that catalyze the limiting steps in the targeted pathways. The objectives ranged from increasing an enzyme's efficiency to enabling it to catalyze a different transformation than the one catalyzed by the wild-type sequence. The steps of enzyme engineering are divided into three major modules: a random mutation generator, an atomistic homology modeler and a binding energy evaluator. This method may therefore build a set of mutant enzymes and filter which sequences are putative candidates for experimental expression and enzymatic testing.

Experimental validation of several case studies highlights the promising performance of the platform to identify suitable natural or mutant enzyme variants for catalyzing specific reactions (Hanko et al., 2023).

These experimental results showcase the potential of enzyme engineering approaches in overcoming challenges in the improvement of metabolic pathways.

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 814408, Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (Portugal) through the R&D unit, FCT project MOSTMICRO-ITQB, with references UIDB/04612/2020 and UIDP/04612/2020 and LS4FUTURE Associated Laboratory (LA/P/0087/2020).

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P56. ADJUSTING THE LIPID PATCH SIZE TO IMPROVE THE REALISM AND EFFICIENCY OF MEMBRANE PROTEIN MD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Aquaporins, MD simulations*

ABSTRACT

Aquaporins (AQPs) are responsible for permeating solutes across membranes. They can be divided into two subgroups: classical aquaporins, strictly selective for water, and aquaglyceroporins, those permeable to water and glycerol. The identification of AQP function modulators has been a difficult task due to the low target druggability and the unsuitability of the commonly used computational approaches. The crystallographic structures of AQPs often present inadequate conformations due to the crystal packing, which impairs the binding of the best modulator candidates. Despite attempts to use computational approaches to mitigate the mentioned problems¹, a fundamental issue remains: are we using the most adequate models, parameters, and force fields to simulate these membrane proteins?

In this work, we initially focused on studying the impact of different membrane sizes on AQPs' stability and function, followed by addressing the impact of different force fields. For this, we set up Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations with the solved structure of the aquaglyceroporin hAQP7 (6QZI)² in a POPC lipid bilayer of different sizes (170, 200, 300, 400, and 500 lipids) with the Amber ff14SB and the CHARMM 36m forcefields.

This protocol helped us understand the conformational behavior of the protein and the membrane and identify the minimal lipid embedding environment required for a fully functional protein.

These results will be useful for the identification of structural features that regulate the function of hAQP7, and later on of specific and efficient functional modulators that could be explored as therapeutic approaches for different diseases.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia for funding through projects UIDB/04046/2020 & UIDP/04046/2020 and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and 2023.03251.BD.

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P57. LEVERAGING AI FOR THE DESIGN OF ANTIBODY-LIKE ENGINEERED PROTEIN SCAFFOLDS

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Keywords: *Viral outbreaks, Monobodies, Computational framework, Antiviral development, Protein language models.*

ABSTRACT

Throughout humanity history, viral outbreaks caused devastating epidemics, like the recent COVID-19, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Over time, SARS-CoV-2 has evolved into different strains with varied characteristics, including immune system and increased infectivity. This highlights the unpredictable nature of future pandemics, needing the development of new methodologies to combat a wide range of viruses. Monobodies, antibody-like engineered proteins derived from the human fibronectin type III that are smaller and simpler than monoclonal antibodies, can be exploited as target-specific antiviral biopharmaceuticals. Therefore, the aim of this project is to create a computational framework and generate a monobody library to streamline the development of target-specific antiviral biopharmaceuticals. Starting from the 10th domain of the human fibronectin type III, we use the protein language model MSA Transformer to generate new monobody sequences, predict their structures using LocalColabFold and dock them with SARS-CoV-2 RBD (Receptor Binding Domain) using MaSIF, as proof-of-concept. Sequence refinement is achieved by iterating over this workflow three times. So far, MSA Transformer has been able to generate over 1.1 million unique sequences, keeping the β -sheets more conserved and the loops more diverse, maintaining the characteristic secondary structure of a monobody. These numbers were achieved by iterative masking. The results obtained so far show the potential of the use of these protein language models on the task of *de novo* sequence generation. The next steps are then to predict the structures of the generated sequences and dock them with the SARS-CoV-2 RBD.

P58. SERINE PROTEASE VviSBT4.19 IN DEFENSE AGAINST *P. VITICOLA*: EXPLORING STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS THROUGH COMPUTATIONAL INSIGHTS

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Keywords: *Grapevine, Serine protease, Plasmopara viticola, Downy mildew, CpHMD*

ABSTRACT

In 2022 Portugal stood as the fifth-largest wine producer in the European Union [1], with its grapevine industry being a vital component of the national economy. However, grapevine pathogens, notably *Plasmopara viticola*, the causative agent of the downy mildew disease, pose significant threats to grape and wine production. Mitigating this challenge without excessive pesticide usage is imperative due to environmental and health concerns. Understanding how tolerant grapevine species recognize and mount successful defense responses against *P. viticola* is thus crucial. Prior studies have underscored the significance of serine proteases, particularly grapevine subtilase VviSBT4.19, in establishing incompatible grapevine-*P. viticola* interactions [2]. While this protease exhibits high expression in resistant genotypes and post-pathogen infection, a comprehensive understanding of its activity modulation by *P. viticola* has been hindered by the lack of a robust structural model.

Here, we present a computational model for VviSBT4.19 constructed using homology modeling (Modeller) [3]. Molecular Dynamics (MD) and Constant-pH MD simulations were subsequently employed to assess the overall stability of the model structure. Our analyses primarily focused on the active site and the relative positioning of the catalytic triad residues to evaluate their topology and functionality. Additionally, we delved into the interactome of VviSBT4.19 and its role in plant immunity. This study aims to bridge existing gaps in understanding the molecular intricacies of grapevine defense against *P. viticola*, potentially laying the groundwork for innovative strategies to bolster disease resistance in grapevine cultivars.

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge financial support from Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through grants CEECIND/02300/2017, 2021.00795.CEECIND, 2021.05909.BD, UI/BD/153055/2022, and 2022.11124.BD and projects UIDB/04046/2020 and UIDP/04046/2020.

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P59. UNRAVELING THE KNOT: INVESTIGATING THE STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS OF UCH-L1 THROUGH MD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Knotted proteins, UCH-L1, Neurodegenerative diseases, MD simulations*

ABSTRACT

Knotted proteins, characterized by embedding an open knot in its native state, gained prominence with the introduction of a knot detection method in 2000 [1]. Nowadays, we know that approximately 1% of PDB entries exhibit knotted structures [2]. Despite intricate folding kinetics, these proteins are evolutionarily conserved and found across all life kingdoms, having functions like enhancing stability and countering degradation [3]. However, a unanimous agreement on a function for knots in proteins remains elusive, largely attributed to a shortage of published research.

This work focuses on UCH-L1, a single-domain protein with a 5₂ knot, renowned for its involvement in the ubiquitin-dependent proteolytic pathway and its implications in neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. UCH-L1 serves as a cysteine protease, featuring a catalytic triad consisting of a cysteine, a histidine, and an aspartic acid. However, in the apo crystal structure of UCH-L1 (2ETL), the catalytic triad is misaligned for catalysis. Intriguingly, the binding of UCH-L1 to ubiquitin (3KW5) induces a conformational rearrangement that brings the catalytic triad residues into closer proximity, thereby promoting enzymatic activity. The unresolved question regarding the specific role of the knot in maintaining the exceptional structural stability of UCH-L1 serves as the primary motivation for this research project. Using molecular dynamics simulations, we aim to explore the conformational space and mechanical stability of knotted UCH-L1. Additionally, we propose a computational approach to investigate truncated variants of UCH-L1, allowing assessment of the impact of knot removal on overall stability and substrate binding affinity.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) for funding through projects UIDB/04046/2020 & UIDP/04046/2020 and grants CEECIND/02300/2017 and UI/BD/153055/2022.

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P60. IMPROVING ADSORPTION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY UNDER VISIBLE LIGHT BY APPLYING FERRITE NANOMATERIALS FUNCTIONALIZED WITH SILVER: THE EXAMPLE OF $\text{Ag}@Zn_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$

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Keywords: *Adsorption, Nanomaterials, Pollutants, Photocatalysis, Visible light.*

ABSTRACT

Exploration of photocatalysis under less energetic wavelengths, i.e. visible light, triggers great interest in the scientific community, as an efficient use of visible light paves the way for harnessing direct sunlight, since the visible spectrum accounts for about 45-50% of the solar spectrum, while UV light only accounts for about 5% [1]. Even under artificial means, the use of visible light is much cheaper than UV light. The pursuit and advancement of new photocatalysts capable of meeting these requirements are of extreme importance, particularly in addressing anthropogenic pollutants, e.g. dyes, pharmaceuticals, pesticides and perfluoroalkyl substances.

In this study, the synthesized and functionalized nanomaterial $\text{Ag}@Zn_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ was characterized, and the photocatalytic activity was tested under visible light, with a model dye solution containing Malachite Green (MG). Ferrite nanomaterials typically present a narrow bandgap, allowing the utilization of visible light [2]. The specific case of $\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ fits perfectly, with an estimated bandgap of 1.80 eV. However, despite the good structural characteristics, ferrites present a high rate of recombination of electrons/holes, limiting their photocatalytic activity. Silver functionalization helps to suppress this limitation by improving the charge separation of electrons/holes, acting as an electron acceptor [3]. The results show a clear effect of silver on the nanomaterials, efficiently removing the model pollutant dye MG under visible light (94.99%) in 0.0125 min^{-1} . Also, the good synergy between adsorption and photocatalysis observed, contributed to the great results.

$\text{Ag}@Zn_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ shows promise for future research, blending effective photocatalysis with superparamagnetic behavior, appealing for industrial application.

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P61. HARNESSING COMPUTER-AIDED STRATEGIES TO IDENTIFY MOLECULAR TARGETS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST THE PINWOOD NEMATODE *BURSAPHELENCHUS XYLOHPILUS*

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Keywords: *Biopesticides, Computer-aided Pesticide Screening, Molecular Targets, Nematicides, Pinewood Nematode.*

ABSTRACT

Plant-parasitic nematodes infect agricultural and forest crops worldwide. The pinewood nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, poses a significant threat to conifer forests in Europe and Asia. Control measures often involve trunk injection of nematicides or spraying insecticides to limit the spread of its vector, *Monochamus* ssp.. Currently, pest management heavily depends on traditional pesticides, the dispersion of which in nature has caused detrimental impacts on the environment and human health. Therefore, there is a pressing need for sustainable alternatives, such as microbial or biochemical biopesticides, to combat plant-parasitic nematodes. Innovative strategies, including computer-aided approaches, have emerged as insightful tools for modeling the molecular recognition between targets and ligands. These methods can easily be seamlessly integrated into the workflow for screening nematotoxic compounds against the pinewood nematode.

A vital initial step in this process is the identification of molecular targets through a literature review.

The literature contains only few reports on the use of *in silico* techniques in the screening of nematicidal compounds against *B. xylophilus*. These studies have primarily focused on two molecular targets: glutamate-gated chloride channel receptors and acetylcholinesterase. Further literature review has highlighted other promising targets, such as chitinase, glutathione *S*-transferase, and phosphoethanolamine methyltransferase.

In this study, an integrated approach that screens for potential eco-friendly bionematicides has been proposed to address the challenge presented by the pinewood nematode.

P62. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO TIGIT INHIBITION FOR CANCER TREATMENT - A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Keywords: *Cancer Therapy, Inhibitors, Small molecules, TIGIT Blockade*

ABSTRACT

TIGIT, an immune checkpoint protein, is frequently overexpressed in many cancer patients, especially within NK and T cells, alongside the co-stimulatory protein DNAM-1. By inhibiting DNAM-1, TIGIT compromises the activation of NK and T cells that are specific to cancer, thereby impairing the immune system's capability to eliminate cancer cells. Despite ongoing efforts to develop inhibitors targeting TIGIT, no candidates have yet been approved, highlighting the urgency for new inhibitors^{1,2}. This study aims to elucidate existing TIGIT-ligand interactions to identify key interactions that are crucial for the design of novel small molecule inhibitors.

Our investigation into TIGIT inhibitors currently in clinical trials involved extensive searches through databases such as ChEMBL, NCI Thesaurus, and the Acro Biosystems database. We acquired core patents of these compounds from the Synapse database for structural analysis. Structures of TIGIT-ligand complexes were retrieved from the PDB and aligned using PyMOL, UCSF Chimera, and MOE to assess structural similarities. Protein-ligand interactions were analyzed using the Protein-Ligand Interaction Profiler (PLIP) software³.

Structural alignments of TIGIT monomers revealed a high degree of similarity, with an α -C RMSD values ranging from 0.36 to 1.15 Å. GLN-56, ILE-68, ASN-70, LEU-73, and TYR-113 were consistently involved in interactions with ligands, forming hydrophobic interactions and/or hydrogen bonds. These residues are likely pivotal for interactions with potential small molecule inhibitors targeting TIGIT.

Our study supports the development of a structure-based pharmacophore model designed to facilitate the identification of novel TIGIT inhibitors.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT): under grant 2023.01201.BD. The authors acknowledge the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia for the financial support under the grants UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020 to iMed. RCG acknowledges funding from LISBOA-01-0246-FEDER-000017, funded by FEDER through COMPETE2020.

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P63. ATP BINDING AS TRIGGER FOR UNDESCRIBED CONFORMATIONAL CHANGES IN ABCG2

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Keywords: *ABC Transporters, ABCG2, Molecular Dynamics, Efflux pump, Conformational Change.*

ABSTRACT

The ABC (ATP-Binding Cassette) protein superfamily is a group of membrane transporters that bind to ATP to perform their function. Their upregulation is a defense strategy against administered drugs, leading to drug resistance, and poor chemotherapy response and prognostic factor.¹ Advances in experimental techniques, such as Cryo-EM, improved the resolution of structural details. However, the full transport mechanism of ABC transporters is still unclear.² Herein, we report the dynamics of the inward-facing conformation of the ABCG2 protein in its apo and ATP-bound states, and the effects of ATP binding.

Homology modelling was used to complete a structure of the ABCG2 protein, starting from a cryo-EM result available on the Protein Data Bank (pdb: 6ETI). Missing sequences were built using our previous BCRP model³ as template along with the PredictProtein secondary structure prediction server⁴. The protein was then inserted into its native environment and under physiological conditions.

We analyzed and compared the conformational changes occurring in the transmembrane and nucleotide binding domains of the ABCG2 apo and ATP-bound forms, providing interesting insights. Our results appear to support a hypothesis proposed by Locher et al⁵ for the ABCG2 efflux mechanism.

Although our research helped elucidate the ABCG2 structural differences between the Apo and ATP-bound forms, further research is required to completely characterize these mechanisms. Nevertheless, a complete understanding of these transporters is essential for anticancer research.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by *Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia*, under contracts UIDP/04567/2020, UIDB/04567/2020, UIDB/04138/2020 and UIDP/04138/2020, and project PTDC/MED-QUI/30591/2017.

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